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D2.2 WorldFAIR's Experience with FIPs (second set of FAIR Implementation Profiles for each case study)

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

AussiESS	Australian Social Survey
CC	Creative Commons
CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
DwC	Darwin Core
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESS	European Social Survey
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FER	FAIR Enabling Resource
FSR	FAIR Supporting Resource
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GFF	GO FAIR Foundation
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums
GloBI	Global Biotic Interactions
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IGSN	International Generic Sample Numbers
InChI	International Chemical Identifier
INSPIRE	Implementation Network for Sharing Population Information from Research Entities

IODE	Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
ODIS	Ocean Data Information System
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
OMOP CDM	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM)
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PARC	Partnership for Assessment of the Risks of Chemicals
PID	Persistent Identifier
PPI	Plant-Pollinator Interactions
PROV-O	PROV (Provenance) Ontology
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SALURBAL	Salud Urbana en América Latina
SDMX	Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards (formerly the Taxonomic Databases Working Group)

Executive summary

This report provides a summary of the experience of the WorldFAIR project using FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs). It briefly revisits the project's interest in the FIPs approach and summarises the use of FIPs by each of the eleven WorldFAIR case study work packages (WPs).

WorldFAIR had a number of objectives in using FIPs:

1. to prompt enquiry and reflection within each case study and discussion among them;
2. to provide insight into current practices, and potentially act as a benchmark of such practices;
3. to help identify any gaps in current FAIR practices and areas requiring further attention;
4. to identify commonalities in experience, culture or practice across the case studies.

These objectives were largely realised, and the experience of the case studies suggests that the process of discussion and reflection was particularly valuable. The fourth objective relates to the development of the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)¹. Here, as intended, the completion of FIPs by the case studies helped refine the initial functional analysis of the requirements for cross-domain FAIR data, and assisted in the identification of some candidate cross-domain standards. **For these reasons, the WorldFAIR project strongly supports the use of FIPs by the global data stewardship community and recommends that investment is made to socialise the approach, and to improve and sustain the necessary infrastructures.**

The report then provides feedback on the use of FIPs. This includes a discussion of what went well and what went less well; considerations from the case studies on how FIPs might best be used; and constructive feedback on how the approach, and the supporting tools and technologies, might be improved. These points are presented as a set of targeted recommendations at the end of the report.

The experience of the WorldFAIR project was that the FIPs exercises were enlightening and useful, both for the case studies and the cross-project synthesis work. The project identified a number of highly beneficial uses for FIPs: as didactic tools; as a useful mechanism for normative declarations of good practice; as a basis for targeted and detailed, domain-specific FAIR assessment; and as a mechanism for identifying commonalities across disciplines and cross-domain solutions. As discussed in our previous report², there was some discussion about the optimal level at which a FIP should be conducted. Notably, it was found that there is an evident utility for FIPs to be developed at the dataset- and the repository- or data service-level. There were recommendations, then, for research disciplines to self-organise globally and encourage FIPs to be developed and published at

¹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/>

² Gregory, A., Hodson, S. (2022). WorldFAIR Project (D2.1) 'FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: What Have We Learnt?' (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378109>

each of these levels. Similarly, it was argued that ‘authoritative organisations’, that represent particular disciplines globally (for example, international scientific unions or global research infrastructures) have a role and responsibility to make sure that the FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) for which they are responsible are published in such a way that they can be referenced in FIPs. Consequently, the WorldFAIR project is strongly supportive of the FIPs approach. A global graph of FERs and FIPs could be a resource of considerable power and benefit.

The WorldFAIR project identified a number of current barriers to achieving this declaration of FERs by responsible organisations. These include the effort required to create FERs and FIPs (including usability issues with the FIP Wizard³) and ease of visualisation (which would provide more immediate value and a sense of reward for undertaking the process). It has been argued that these barriers could be (at least partly) overcome by the wholesale integration of FER information from the FAIRsharing resource⁴, which curates information about standards and other FERs, and a change in the technical underpinnings.

To accelerate progress towards achieving this vision of a global graph of FERs and FIPs, it would be hugely beneficial to find a mechanism for the wholesale integration of FAIRsharing entries as FERs that can be identified in FIPs. Is such a solution organisationally and technically possible? **The WorldFAIR project recommends that options to enable the wholesale use of FAIRsharing information as FERs in FIPs be explored by the parties involved and by the community as a whole.**

It was also argued, notably by WorldFAIR WP11 (Ocean Sciences), that a shift from the use of nanopublication to JSON-LD/schema.org would provide technological underpinnings that better allow the creation of tools to analyse and visualise FIPs, facilitating the engagement of a wider developer base. Based on a widely-used web format, it would also be easier to harvest declared FIPs and FERs for this purpose. In response, the GO FAIR Foundation team behind the FIPs initiative contend that this would result in semantic loss (particularly in relation to the provenance of the statement and the way in which the nanopublication wraps the set of declarations in FERs and FIPs). Is it possible to find a way of harmonising the nanopublication approach favoured by GO FAIR with the JSON-LD/schema.org approach suggested above? **The WorldFAIR project recommends that effort is dedicated to aligning and harmonising these approaches in order to enable the FAIR community and the multitude of disciplines to achieve the objectives of the FIPs approach and vision.**

In responding to Recommendation 4 of the ‘Turning FAIR into Reality’ report⁵, WorldFAIR has been motivated by a conviction that any assessment of FAIR practices needs to be informed by the requirements of research domains and cross-domain research areas. In approaches to FAIR

³ <https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/>

⁴ <https://fairsharing.org/>

⁵ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Turning FAIR into reality – Final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>

assessment, the question set underlying the various existing FAIR assessment tools is concerned with **whether** the repository or dataset uses (for example) a FAIR-compliant identifier or vocabulary. In contrast, the FIPs question set asks the user to specify **which** vocabulary (or other FER) is being used. This is a far more useful exercise. In time, FIPs can provide a model against which FAIR assessment can be based, reflecting both the current practice, and the aspirations of a given community or research domain. A number of the WorldFAIR case studies argued that the utility of FIPs and FERs could be increased even more by adding further information about how the FER is implemented, adding an important dimension for data and metadata validation. In time, if CDIF plays the role envisaged, it will be useful for FIPs to make specific reference to how the CDIF recommendations and profiles are implemented.

Finally, the report also provides some example visualisations of the WorldFAIR FIPs in the form of a 'FAIR Convergence Matrix', and in the form of a graph that shows connections between FIPs, FERs and the communities using them. The report also draws some initial conclusions about how such analysis and visualisation can be used to identify commonalities across the disciplines represented.

Table of contents

Executive summary	6
1. Introduction	11
2. How WorldFAIR uses FIPs	11
3. Summary of the WPs' use of FIPs	12
3.1 WP03 Chemistry	13
3.2 WP04 Nanomaterials	15
3.3 WP05 Geochemistry	16
3.4 WP06 Social Surveys	19
3.5 WP07 Population Health	19
3.6 WP08 Urban Health	20
3.7 WP09 Biodiversity	23
3.8 WP10 Agricultural Biodiversity	24
3.9 WP11 Ocean Sciences	26
3.10 WP12 Disaster Risk Reduction	27
3.11 WP13 Cultural Heritage	28
4. Feedback on the FIPs	29
4.1 What is the utility of FIPs?	29
4.1.1 Stimulating reflection on FAIR practices and identifying gaps	29
4.1.2 Reference and model for data stewardship	30
4.1.3 Role in FAIR compliance and assessment	30
4.1.4 Identifying commonalities across domains	30
4.2 Discussion of how best to use FIPs	32
4.2.1 Level of use: domain, community, repository, dataset?	32
4.3 What must be improved in the FIPs approach?	33
4.3.1 Encoding of FERs and Nanopublications	35
4.3.2 Role of sponsoring or authoritative organisations	35
4.4 An alternative to nanopublications for FIPs?	37
4.4.1 An ODIS FIP using JSON-LD/schema.org	37
4.4.2 WP11's case for the benefits of the ODIS FIP approach	40
5. Next steps: global graph of FERs and FIPs?	41
6. Information in FERs and FIPs	42
6.1 Data provenance, processing and lineage	43
7. Analysis of the WorldFAIR FIPs	44

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7.1 Examples of influence of FIPs across domains / case studies	51
8. Conclusions	51
9. Recommendations	53
References / bibliography	56

1. Introduction

This report provides a summary of the experience of the WorldFAIR project using FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs). It briefly revisits the project's interest in the FIPs approach and summarises the use of FIPs by each of the eleven WorldFAIR case study work packages.

The report then provides feedback on the use of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs). This includes a discussion of what went well and what went less well, considerations from the case studies on how FIPs might best be used, as well as constructive feedback on how the approach, and the supporting tools and technologies, might be improved. These points are presented as a set of targeted recommendations at the end of the report.

The report also provides some example visualisations of the WorldFAIR FIPs in the form of a 'FAIR Convergence Matrix', and in the form of graphs that highlight FERs that are shared among communities. The report also draws some initial conclusions about how such analysis and visualisation can be used to identify commonalities across the disciplines represented.

The discussion, conclusion and recommendations that follow are drawn from the experiences of the WorldFAIR project and its case study work packages. When the source is one of the WorldFAIR reports, this is referenced in a footnote. When the source is one of the many meetings and workshops, and the notes therefrom, the argument is attributed to the case study work package that made it, as follows: (WP02 - Synthesis).

2. How WorldFAIR uses FIPs

FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) are a methodology developed by the GO FAIR initiative⁶, through which a research community expresses its practices and decisions around FAIR. The approach involves a series of questions on how the community makes data and metadata FAIR and what 'FAIR Enabling Resources' (FERs) are used to address each of the FAIR principles.

The WorldFAIR project's interest in FIPs, and use of FIPs with the WorldFAIR case studies, was described in detail in Deliverable 2.1 'FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: What Have We Learnt?'⁷ The project explored FIPs through each of the eleven case studies: FIPs were developed by each case study early in the project and again towards the end of the project. The FIPs produced by the WorldFAIR case studies are available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/worldfair-project-fips/> and can be used as examples to be

⁶ <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>

⁷ Gregory, A., Hodson, S. (2022). WorldFAIR Project (D2.1) 'FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: What Have We Learnt?' (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378109>

replicated and to facilitate FAIR data practices for the disciplines addressed by the project and beyond.

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1. to prompt enquiry and reflection within each case study and discussion among them;
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These objectives were largely realised, and the experience of each of the case studies suggests that the process of discussion and reflection was particularly valuable. The fourth objective point relates to the development of the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)⁸. Here, as intended, the completion of FIPs by the case studies helped refine the initial functional analysis of the requirements for cross-domain FAIR data, and assisted in the identification of some candidate cross-domain standards.

WorldFAIR has also been motivated by the conviction that any assessment of FAIR practices needs to be informed by the requirements of research domains and cross-domain research areas. In approaches to FAIR assessment, the question set underlying the various existing FAIR assessment tools are concerned with **whether** the repository or dataset uses (for example) a FAIR-compliant identifier or vocabulary. In contrast, the FIPs question set asks the user to specify **which** vocabulary (or other FER) is being used. This is a far more useful exercise. And it is clear, in time, that FIPs can provide a model against which FAIR assessment can be based, reflecting both the current practice, and the aspirations of a given community or research domain⁹.

It was also intended that the use of FIPs by the WorldFAIR case studies would provide a useful reflection on the FIPs methodology and approach, and constructive feedback on the question set and the FIP Wizard online tool. This is reflected in the feedback from the case studies that follows.

3. Summary of the WPs' use of FIPs

This section summarises and characterises the approach taken to FIPs by each of the WorldFAIR case study work packages (WPs 03 - 11). These FIPs have been gathered for reference in the WorldFAIR FIPs community on Zenodo¹⁰.

⁸ WorldFAIR D2.3 Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236871>

⁹ See Gregory, A., Hodson, S. (2024). WorldFAIR (D2.4) Recommendations and framework for FAIR Assessment within (and across) disciplines (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11242737>, for more on this topic.

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/communities/worldfair-project-fips/>

Figure 1. The final FIPs produced by each WorldFAIR Work Package.

3.1 WP03 Chemistry

Completed FIPs: International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) standards as FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs)¹¹, IUPAC Gold Book¹².

Account of FIPs experience in reports: D3.1 'Digital recommendations for Chemistry FAIR data policy and practice', pp. 42-44 (discussion of FERs, FIPs and CDIF in chemistry and across domains) and pp. 59-67 (FIPs)¹³.

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11385625>; FIP Nanopublication: https://w3id.org/np/RAI5DIMmJvgLi5nXNPV_CqgisMb-mq4T5HK2ZX4fUctyo; FIP Wizard: <https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/f5bf44ef-39c1-4ddf-99d1-27331cdeff00>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11388770>; FIP Nanopublication: http://purl.org/np/RAWPrqabwHD1EhI9OUcd_AhSWfpLODUHJIBH6RIhOoRQA; FIP Wizard: <https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/04ba76bc-d747-4050-93a0-bdaaecc157d6>

¹³ McEwen, L., Bruno, I. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D3.1) Digital recommendations for Chemistry FAIR data policy and practice (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887283>

The IUPAC-led Chemistry case study produced three FIPs over the course of the project:

1. Organisational level FAIR Implementation Profile of IUPAC-stewarded FAIR Enabling Resources collectively (i.e. “a general assessment of IUPAC digital standards and their respective functions as FERs”);
2. FAIR Implementation Profile of a specific IUPAC FER resource (i.e. “a more specific assessment of the IUPAC Gold Book Compendium of Chemical Terminology¹⁴ as a FAIR vocabulary”); and
3. FAIR Implementation Profile of a community data resource implementing a range of FERs (formal and de facto standards) for chemical information.

The first two FIPs were used to help understand 1) the “FAIR application of IUPAC standards in supporting chemistry data exchange” and 2) “the FAIR status of IUPAC standards for those who need to use them”. The goal was “to provide some indication of FAIR application of IUPAC standards in supporting chemistry data exchange” and the status of IUPAC standards as FAIR Enabling Resources, rather than broad practices of implementing FAIR in the domain.¹⁵ The FIPs exercise and tools were generally viewed as useful in this respect.

In general, it was felt that the FIPs exercise was useful for reflection on the role of chemistry standards: “Working from the premise that standards from IUPAC and other authoritative bodies provide the scientific backbone for accurate chemistry data exchange, we can consider two questions relative to the FIP analysis: 1) how do these standards fit into the FER typology to enable FAIR re-use of chemistry data?; and 2) are these standards themselves available in forms that are FAIR and accessible for programmatic re-use?”¹⁶

The answers to these questions point to a responsibility of IUPAC to continue to maintain essential chemistry resources as FERs. The intention is for the ‘Gold Book FIP’ to be reviewed every two years and on the occasion of any resource upgrades in order to inform priorities for further development. To realise benefits, however, a critical mass of FIPs for IUPAC standards would be necessary. This poses resourcing challenges and also raises questions about whether the current approach to creating and encoding FIPs is optimal. IUPAC is working with the international chemistry community to develop a map of chemistry standards relative to their function in enabling chemical data exchange: the general approach used for FIP questions and the FER typology would likely be useful for this research and analysis. Building on these semantics, the approach to encoding FERs and FIPs suggested by WP11 Oceanography below may allow the machine-actionable description of FERs to better scale across community projects.

¹⁴ The IUPAC Compendium of Chemical Terminology (Gold Book). <https://doi.org/10.1351/goldbook>

¹⁵ McEwen, L., Bruno, I. (2023), p.43.

¹⁶ McEwen, L., Bruno, I. (2023), p.43.

3.2 WP04 Nanomaterials

Completed FIP(s): Broad community practice¹⁷; NanoPharos database¹⁸.

Account of FIPs experience in reports: D4.1 ‘Nanomaterials domain-specific FAIRification mapping’, pp.59-74 (‘As-Is’ Nanomaterials FIP)¹⁹; D4.2 ‘NanoPharos FAIR Implementation Profile’, pp.73-91 (NanoPharos FIP).²⁰

The Nanomaterials and Nanosafety-focused WP04, involving a number of institutions with links to European projects, produced two FIPs. The first was a general ‘subject-level’ Nanomaterials and Nanosafety FIP which was helpful to obtain an ‘As-Is’ characterisation of the state of play in relation to FAIR implementation, including a gap analysis²¹. The second was a FIP for the NanoPharos database that offers users open access high-quality datasets in a ready-for-modelling tabular format. This was important for the needs analysis and provided useful pointers for how to increase the FAIRness of the database in certain respects, as well as supporting “the integration into NanoPharos of relevant ontologies to ensure that all data and metadata are machine understandable and actionable”.²²

The Nanomaterials WP noted the utility of FIPs as the basis for discussions about FAIR practices with contiguous disciplines: “the As-Is FIP will be updated at the end of the WorldFAIR project, to capture: the rapid development in the field; our own efforts to enhance the number of domain-specific FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) and FAIR Supporting Resources (FSRs); FIPs underway in the aforementioned WorldFAIR Chemistry (WP03) and Geochemistry (WP05) case studies, as well as the efforts underway in the Partnership for Assessment of the Risks of Chemicals (PARC), which has a very strong FAIR data focus.”²³

The FIPs exercises also formed a strong basis for the analysis of FERs in nanomaterials, including discussions of FAIR software and FAIR models²⁴. It is evident that the nanomaterials-nanosafety

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386015>; FIP Nanopublication:
https://w3id.org/np/RAma4YJFMH2VoShlPwD6eMGX_TZtYNoDnUM641yokDeRc; FIP Wizard:
<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/b0d84171-4556-46ed-9ace-c1c58db38092>

¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11385683>; FIP Nanopublication:
https://w3id.org/np/RA_72X3YOdeWiLD-xUoBvQUdTX7dXyKLDakXw2dCkqMQk; FIP Wizard:
<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/f1c10e5a-2094-4c00-9afe-7d7eca3bb6f8>

¹⁹ Lynch, I., Afantitis, A., Exner, T., Papadiamantis, A. (2023). WorldFAIR (D4.1) Nanomaterials domain-specific FAIRification mapping (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887341>

²⁰ Lynch, I., Afantitis, A. (2024). WorldFAIR (D4.2) FAIRification of nanoinformatics tools and models recommendations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10629631>

²¹ Lynch, I., Afantitis, A., Exner, T., Papadiamantis, A. (2023), pp. 42-47.

²² Lynch, I., Afantitis, A. (2024), p. 40, p. 73.

²³ Lynch, I., Afantitis, A., Exner, T., Papadiamantis, A. (2023), p. 6.

²⁴ Lynch, I., Afantitis, A. (2024), pp. 32-50.

community sees benefit in the approach of using FIPs and FERs and will continue to explore this in the context of PARC and other initiatives.

3.3 WP05 Geochemistry

Completed FIP(s): WorldFAIR WP05 Geochemistry Reference FIP (v1)²⁵; Repository-level FIP²⁶ for GFZ Data Services²⁷; Repository-level FIP²⁸ for EarthChem Library²⁹; Repository-level FIP³⁰ for AusGeochem the AuScope Geochemistry Network's data platform³¹; and Repository-level FIP³² for GEOROC (Geochemistry of Rocks of the Oceans and Continents)³³.

Account of FIPs experience in reports: WorldFAIR MS6 'Geochemistry Scientific Content Component', (A Proposed Methodology to Develop and Update FIPs), pp. 7-9³⁴; D5.2 'Geochemistry Methodology and Outreach'³⁵; D5.3 'Guidelines for implementing Geochemistry FIPs'³⁶.

WP05 Geochemistry, led by AuScope and involving the OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group³⁷ to engage with geochemistry stakeholders and data infrastructures, quickly came to the conclusion that developing a single FAIR Implementation Profile representing all geochemistry communities or for all geochemical data will not be possible; rather, there will need to be multiple FIPs for geochemistry communities, subdisciplines and at multiple levels of data granularity. Consequently, the approach taken in WP05 has been to explore and examine the utility of FIPs and FERs for

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11373659>

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11385479>; FIP Wizard

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/a74bb38b-f1f7-41ce-9e06-2be278c561cc>

²⁷ <https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/portal/index.html>

²⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11385528>; FIP Wizard

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/39201002-c73d-4ce6-871c-dee1cfb0a9a0>

²⁹ <https://www.earthchem.org/ecl/>

³⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11385569>; FIP Wizard

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/51f2a090-63cd-4580-91bc-862381c39f91>

³¹ <https://www.auscope.org.au/ausgeochem>

³² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11395426>; FIP Nanopublication

https://w3id.org/np/RABWe7ZkKlI7YfDPXPR6PVC9PWIX_Kjqc58AwU8T0F1s; FIP Wizard

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/154ad866-eba3-4c33-9a3b-3f8276cdaf17>

³³ <https://georoc.eu/georoc/new-start.asp>

³⁴ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R., Lehnert, K., Klöcking, M., Elger, K., Hezel, D., ter Maat, G., Profeta, L., Rawling, T. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (MS6) Geochemistry Scientific Content Component (1.1). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7977116>

³⁵ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R. (2024a). WorldFAIR (D5.2) Geochemistry Methodology and Outreach (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10406332>

³⁶ Prent, A., Farrington, R., Wyborn, L., Nixon, A., Elger, K., Klöcking, M., Hezel, D., Lehnert, K. (2024b). WorldFAIR (D5.3) Guidelines for implementing Geochemistry FIPs (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10712808>

³⁷ <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/worldfair/onegeochemistry-wg/>

geochemistry-specific data repositories characterised by a community that includes a number of sub-disciplines and uses a variety of analytical techniques and data types³⁸.

The Geochemistry case study viewed FIPs and FERs as useful tools: “A FIP is an excellent tool that firstly provides a standardised method for geochemists to provide machine-readable information on how a specific dataset is described and compiled. Secondly, when FIPs become available in the community they can serve as a guide to understanding the scientific resources and technologies utilised by specific geochemical communities. FIPs can offer insights into the FAIR evolution of a dataset or a community. FIPs can also serve as a tool for data producers and data providers (infrastructures), who can refer to a specific dataset’s FIP to provide the information required to understand and (re)use the dataset.”³⁹ Furthermore, when targeted at the level of repositories, the WP found “the generation and use of FIPs an effective tool to pinpoint commonalities between existing systems and highlight where the community can improve.”⁴⁰

In concordance with WP03 (Chemistry) it became clear to the Geochemistry case study that a lot rests on the publication of FERs by the community. It is a declared task for the OneGeochemistry WG “to engage and motivate community repositories and databases to share their FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) in a FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP). From the various FIPs, common FERs can be extracted to be published ... that will help repositories and databases to become more FAIR (especially facilitating interoperability).”⁴¹ For this reason, the Geochemistry work package developed a Geochemistry Reference FIP.⁴² This product is by no means comprehensive, but it does “provide an overview of the resources being used by geochemistry repositories, databases, platforms and collaborating infrastructures currently active in the WorldFAIR project.” The Geochemistry Reference FIP is intended as a living document and the basis for a future Geochemistry Best Practice System website,⁴³ which would be modelled on the Oceans Best Practices System website⁴⁴. The purpose of the Reference FIP, and the report that inter alia describes it, is “to provide a reference source, or a catalogue of available FERs that are being used by WP05-associated geochemistry data repositories. This reference catalogue can be consulted and used by laboratories and repositories, as a means to encourage reuse of available resources and prevent ‘reinventing of the wheel’.”⁴⁵

³⁸ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R., Lehnert, K., Klöcking, M., Elger, K., Hezel, D., ter Maat, G., Profeta, L., Rawling, T. (2023), p.4.

³⁹ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R. (2024a), p.22.

⁴⁰ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R. (2024a), p.24.

⁴¹ Prent, A., Rawling, T. (2022). WorldFAIR Project (D5.1) Formalisation of OneGeochemistry (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7380947>

⁴² WorldFAIR WP05 Geochemistry Reference FIP (v1): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11373659>. The concept DOI for all versions is 10.5281/zenodo.11373658.

⁴³ Prent, A., Farrington, R., Wyborn, L., Nixon, A., Elger, K., Klöcking, M., Hezel, D., Lehnert, K. (2024b), p. 10.

⁴⁴ <https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/>

⁴⁵ Prent, A., Farrington, R., Wyborn, L., Nixon, A., Elger, K., Klöcking, M., Hezel, D., Lehnert, K. (2024b), p. 7.

This manner of using the FIP approach, to publicise which FERs are being used in any tier of the community, was viewed as the best currently-available way of clearly categorising FERs under the FAIR principles and encouraging adoption and convergence, thereby paving the way to greater interoperability and reusability for geochemical data across the community.

The goal of the resource, in sum, is “to facilitate the implementation of commonly-used FERs, and so improv[e] data FAIRness, with a resource that fosters interoperability, accelerates convergence on data standards, and ultimately enhances the accessibility and reusability of geochemical data.”⁴⁶

A further consideration is that the knowledge of which FERs are in use “can also drive the development of mappings and crosswalks between actively-used FERs, furthering interoperability between geochemistry communities. The incorporation of more generically-used FERs from interdisciplinary areas can lead to cross-domain interoperability which will be increasingly sought after in the near future.”⁴⁷

The Geochemistry case study’s final report includes recommendations that constitute a call to action for the global community, emphasising the importance of publicising FERs:

1. A geochemistry website should be built that follows on the example of the Oceans Best Practice initiative where FERs from the reference FIP and other resources can be published, promulgated and updated by the relevant local, regional, international and global communities.
2. A call should go out to the geochemistry community to list their existing FERs used in respective repositories and data-producing facilities into the living document, so the reference FIP can grow and stimulate convergence.
3. Data infrastructures are recommended to document their own FIPs utilising the reference FIP and other FERs as per their current or planned future practice.
4. Similar FERs should be identified and discussions about building crosswalks between them should be initiated.⁴⁸

⁴⁶ Prent, A., Farrington, R., Wyborn, L., Nixon, A., Elger, K., Klöcking, M., Hezel, D., Lehnert, K. (2024b), p. 4.

⁴⁷ Prent, A., Farrington, R., Wyborn, L., Nixon, A., Elger, K., Klöcking, M., Hezel, D., Lehnert, K. (2024b), p. 9.

⁴⁸ Prent, A., Farrington, R., Wyborn, L., Nixon, A., Elger, K., Klöcking, M., Hezel, D., Lehnert, K. (2024b), p.12.

3.4 WP06 Social Surveys

Completed FIP(s): FIPs at the level of data services (ADA⁴⁹ and Sikt⁵⁰) managing the Australian Social Survey (AussiESS)⁵¹ and the European Social Survey (ESS)⁵²: AussiESS FIP⁵³, ESS FIP⁵⁴.

Account of FIPs experience in reports: D6.1 ‘Cross-national Social Sciences survey FAIR implementation case studies’, pp. 24-27 (FIP).⁵⁵

WorldFAIR WP06 focussed on the highly relevant issue of harmonising social survey data, with the specific example of harmonisation between the European Social Survey and the Australian Social Survey. FIPs were used in this work package as part of an initial exercise, along with other questions and considerations, to “provide an overview of the current practices with FAIR data standards ... to compare and contrast the practices between the Australian Data Archive and Sikt.no”. The use of FIPs helped identify shared infrastructural needs (such as registries) and fed into the WP’s early recommendations.

The subsequent focus of the work package has been on the very specific challenge of data and metadata harmonisation between the two surveys. This is conducted at a level of detail and specificity beyond that usefully covered in FIPs and which assumes the use of a number of FERs, particularly the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) and Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange (SDMX) standards widely used in social sciences and statistics.⁵⁶ The recommendations from WP06 are of significant relevance to WorldFAIR WP08 (Urban Health), which also faces the challenges of data and metadata harmonisation.

3.5 WP07 Population Health

Completed FIP(s): Project-level FIP⁵⁷ for the INSPIRE Population Health data platform⁵⁸.

⁴⁹ <https://ada.edu.au/>

⁵⁰ <https://sikt.no/>

⁵¹ <https://dataverse.ada.edu.au/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.26193/HMPLAT>

⁵² <https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/>

⁵³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386096>

⁵⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386096>

⁵⁵ McEachern, S., Orten, H., Thome Petersen, H., Perry, R. (2023a). WorldFAIR Project (D6.1) Cross-national Social Sciences survey FAIR implementation case studies (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599652>

⁵⁶ McEachern, S., Orten, H., Perry, R., Strand, K. (2023b). WorldFAIR (D6.2) Cross-national Social Sciences survey best practice guidelines (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8308012> and McEachern, S., Orten, H., Perry, R., Strand, K. (2024). WorldFAIR (D6.3) Pilot Testing Harmonisation Workflows (Version 1). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10724744>

⁵⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386340>; FIP Wizard:

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/Ofd0f808-f847-488f-a7e3-d33d25314313>; FIP nanopublication:

<https://w3id.org/np/RAVu31pXmmZvL6PG39Pg0MYkf53p7GZ0RS0rDezEautws>

⁵⁸ <https://aphrc.org/inspire/>

Account of FIPs experience in reports: D7.1 ‘Implementation Guidelines for Annotating Health Research Data and Harmonisation: The INSPIRE Approach’, pp. 8-9 (Summary).⁵⁹

WorldFAIR Work Package 07, on Population Health, used FIPs to characterise population health studies and particularly the use of the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) in the data platform prepared for the INSPIRE projects. The exercise assisted in identifying areas where OMOP data might not be considered FAIR.

The Work Package team spent considerable time and effort exploring how to use FIPs and FERs to characterise resources in Population Health generally and in the INSPIRE series of projects specifically. FIPs and FERs were found to be useful as an approach to initiate analysis of the FAIRness of the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) and related resources.

The team observed that the FIPs approach was not the only way that this analysis could have been stimulated and conducted. New to FAIR terminology and, in particular some of the specific jargon around FIPs and FERs, the team struggled at first and found the FIP Wizard confusing. However, once the team had better understood and assimilated the notion of a ‘FAIR Enabling Resource’, the process became easier to follow and did help highlight some immediate and priority steps that could be taken in relation to the data systems and the use of the OMOP CDM.

This said, in parallel with the experience of WP06 on Social Surveys, the FIPs approach was found to be a useful introduction to FAIR and a means of performing an analysis of practice. Very quickly, however, the level of detail and granularity went beyond that covered by the FIPs and the identification of the use of given FERs. The most important thing in the end was to produce implementation guides to adopt FAIR data practice in the case study research area.

3.6 WP08 Urban Health

Completed FIP(s): Project-level FIP⁶⁰ as a baseline guide for good practice in urban health and for the Salud Urbana en América Latina (SALURBAL⁶¹) project⁶².

⁵⁹ Gregory, A., Todd, J., Amadi, D., Greenfield, J., Muyingo, S., Tomlin, K. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D7.1) Population Health Data Implementation Guide (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887385>

⁶⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386370>; FIP Wizard:

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/eba0fa97-3c1d-4ce4-84e7-0af69b9d9bc0>

⁶¹ <https://drexel.edu/lac/salurbal/overview/>

⁶² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11395447>; FIP Wizard:

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/2f92844d-736a-43ca-ab05-9d3908fb8e87>

Account of FIPs experience in reports: D8.1 ‘Urban Health Data - Guidelines and Recommendations’, pp. 11-14 (discussion) and pp. 28-57 (FAIR Primer for the SALURBAL data platform)⁶³; D8.2 ‘Urban Health Data - Learning and training’, pp. 22-36 (Improved FAIR Implementation Profile).⁶⁴

WorldFAIR WP08 on Urban Health used FIPs to assess the implementation of FAIR principles within the Urban Health field in two ways. First, the elaboration of a web data platform for the SALURBAL project (Urban Health in Latin America) was informed by considerations from the FIPs exercise. Second, the team developed a FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) for the Urban Health discipline in general.

The WP08 team found the process of filling out the FIP Wizard to be very useful: it enabled and focussed reflection on the FAIR principles and allowed the team to engage with their own project workflow, more rigorously within the framework of the various specific FAIR requirements. Furthermore, the discussions of FIPs and the other opportunities to engage across domains in the WorldFAIR project was invaluable to develop a better understanding of practices in other domains, which could be beneficial for urban health. Specifically, this included the adoption of controlled vocabularies in SALURBAL’s FAIR implementation. The experience was invaluable in building a strong semantic and implementational foundation of FAIR from which future urban health projects could build on.

“The FAIR Implementation Profile for the SALURBAL case study contributed to the renovation process that the data system was undergoing, offering valuable guidance on good practices currently possible for making data FAIR.” Areas highlighted included:

1. the need to promote a deeper understanding of the FAIR principles among urban health researchers and practitioners;
2. the utility of systematically using a data management plan during the design and initial steps of a research project that can guide the implementation of FAIR principles across different domains and working groups;
3. the need to use persistent identifiers for a number commonly used digital objects, particularly spatial visualisations of urban health data;
4. the lack of a common repository for urban health data;
5. the strong advantages of adopting the DDI standards and a more systematic and coordinated approach to the use of vocabularies and other semantics.

As noted above, the FIPs exercise and related work drawing on the experience of the SALURBAL project helped draw attention to the lack of a common repository for urban health data. “Although a great amount of data used in urban health research can be also found in repositories traditionally

⁶³ Ortigoza, A., Moore, K., Quitsberg, A., Li, R., Lazo-Elizondo, M., & Diez Roux, A. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D8.1) Urban Health Data - Guidelines and Recommendations (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887523>

⁶⁴ Bilal, U., Ortigoza, A., Li, R., & Anderson, T. (2024). WorldFAIR (D8.2) Urban health data - learning and training (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731625>

used in social research such as the one developed by the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR), most of the data regarding the built and natural environment in cities is spread across different platforms using bespoke codebooks.”⁶⁵ Furthermore, the FIPs exercise revealed the inconsistent use of metadata and controlled vocabularies across urban health data: the activity showed that most urban health data could, and should, be encoded following the DDI standards⁶⁶.

Responding to these recommendations, the team creating the SALURBAL data platform incorporated the FAIR principles, and looked for FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) within the urban health discipline. “This helped restructure the data and metadata records for the project, with a standardisation of identifiers (variable and dataset names), and datasets and data protocol formats that consequently enabled the reorganisation of the data structure to increase and improve findability, interoperability, and reuse of the data through machine-actionable mechanisms.”⁶⁷

Secondly, the results of the FIP were used “to create a web resource (‘A FAIR Primer’) which [...] provides information about the FAIR principles, relays some of the FIP’s findings and provides guidance for making SALURBAL data more FAIR”. This resource is accessible at <https://drexel-uhc.github.io/salurbal-project-dashboard/>.

Further work is required to provide guidance on Interoperability and Reusability, as the SALURBAL FIP identified a number of gaps, e.g. in relation to the use of FAIR vocabularies (I2) and the provision of provenance and processing metadata (R1.2). Some of this can be addressed by engagement with the DDI standards, good practices in related communities and the WorldFAIR CDIF recommendations.

The updated FAIR Implementation Profile describes the SALURBAL team’s efforts “to harmonise multi-country urban health data, aiming to create a machine-actionable resource that aligns with the FAIR principles.” This is a critical step to address the data management complexities of urban health research and to develop a pragmatic approach to the harmonisation of extensive datasets across various countries and domains. Like the other social science case studies, this work is done at a level of detail below that covered by the FIPs and FERs. The need for harmonising controlled vocabularies and the use of a metadata standard like DDI is recognised. But the process also highlighted a need for reflection on the requirements of data engineering, and in particular the need for a platform that enables multidimensional modelling.⁶⁸ This points also to the need for further work to characterise data provenance and processing: “One of the key aspects of the FIP we

⁶⁵ Ortigoza, A., Moore, K., Quitsberg, A., Li, R., Lazo-Elizondo, M., Diez Roux, A. (2023), p.13. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887523>

⁶⁶ Ortigoza, A., Moore, K., Quitsberg, A., Li, R., Lazo-Elizondo, M., Diez Roux, A. (2023), pp.4, 13, 24. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887523>

⁶⁷ Ortigoza, A., Moore, K., Quitsberg, A., Li, R., Lazo-Elizondo, M., Diez Roux, A. (2023), pp.14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887523>

⁶⁸ Bilal, U., Ortigoza, A., Li, R., & Anderson, T. (2024), pp.22-39. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731625>

want to develop further is data provenance infrastructure - or tracking meta(data) as it goes through layers of transformation. There are industry workflows such as Data Built Tools (DBT) to build well-organised data warehouses but these are not commonly utilised in academic settings. In the future, we hope to explore the integration feasibility between the data provenance systems (e.g., DBT) and a FAIR meta(data) inventory.”⁶⁹

3.7 WP09 Biodiversity

Completed FIP(s): Model-level FIP as a description of the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) draft Core Unified Data Model⁷⁰

Account of FIPs experience in reports: D9.1 ‘Data standard for sharing ecological and environmental monitoring data documented for community review’, p. 4 (summary)⁷¹; D9.2 ‘Community consultation and finalisation of Biodiversity FAIR data impact’, p. 4 (summary)⁷².

The focus of WP09 activity was to contribute to the development of the draft core Unified Data Model for GBIF. “Darwin Core (DwC), the most commonly used data standard in the GBIF community, has provided a simple and effective framework for supporting the growth of species occurrence data available from the GBIF network: its use has been critical in enabling the the GBIF community to build evidence of 2.3 billion species occurrence events since 2001.”⁷³

However, the GBIF and TDWG communities have been aware for some time of the limitations encountered in the use of DwC for the increasing wide range of data sources and data types. Recognising the tension between ease of use and loss of information in an oversimplified model, the DwC community has encouraged the expansion of data publishing capabilities to supply missing semantic rigour.

The GBIF 20-year review⁷⁴, conducted by CODATA, recommended maintaining and building on GBIF’s status as the most comprehensive source of biodiversity data. “The CODATA review acknowledges

⁶⁹ Bilal, U., Ortigoza, A., Li, R., & Anderson, T. (2024), pp.44. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731625>

⁷⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386417>; FIP Wizard

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/b588052c-22da-4671-a19e-f68f773ab70f>; FIP Nanopublication: <http://purl.org/np/RAkH0yo5VWU0qfkrYOyJRQINeJJJC0B659E8GqyHtC2eQ>

⁷¹ Miller, J., Robertson, T., Wieczorek, J. (2023a). WorldFAIR Project (D9.1) Data standard for sharing ecological and environmental monitoring data documented for community review (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849241>

⁷² Miller, J., Robertson, T., Wieczorek, J. (2023b). WorldFAIR (D9.2) Community consultation and finalisation of Biodiversity FAIR data impact: Final data model and training materials completed and shared (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10058058>

⁷³ Miller, J., Robertson, T., Wieczorek, J. (2023a). WorldFAIR Project (D9.1), p.6. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849241>

⁷⁴ CODATA, the Committee on Data of the International Science Council, Pfeiffenberger, H., Uhlir, P., Hodson, S. (2020). Twenty-Year Review of GBIF. <https://doi.org/10.35035/ctzm-hz97>

the issues associated with the complexity of biodiversity data and identifies the need to accommodate more varied data types to meet growing research needs.”⁷⁵

The new Unified Model “was developed in collaboration with the Biodiversity Information Standards Group (TDWG) and through community consultation via webinars, open drafting of documents and solicitation of test datasets from the various stakeholders.” In particular, the WorldFAIR collaboration enabled the incorporation of a camera trap use case, as well as the further development, consultation and socialisation of the new Unified Data Model.⁷⁶

Consequently, the GBIF WP09 FIP focuses on the Unified Model, which itself aims to maximise the interoperability of biodiversity data. The updated reference FIP reflects this improved functionality. The FIPs exercise was useful for engaging with the FAIR terminology and for understanding and expressing the Unified Model’s functionality in FAIR terms. In particular, the FIPs development, and other activities and discussions in WorldFAIR, were “useful in identifying and articulating steps for cross-domain interaction, particularly with Agricultural Biodiversity, Oceans, and Geochemistry.”⁷⁷

3.8 WP10 Agricultural Biodiversity

Completed FIP(s): Community level FIP on plant-pollinator interactions data⁷⁸.

Account of FIPs experience in reports: D10.1 ‘Agriculture-related pollinator data standards use cases report’, p. 14 (summary)⁷⁹; D10.3 ‘Agricultural biodiversity FAIR data assessment rubrics’, pp. 8-12 (Rubric for assessment of plant-pollinator interactions data), pp. 26-36 (FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) for plant-pollinator interactions data)⁸⁰.

WorldFAIR WP10 on Agricultural Biodiversity, specialising in plant-pollinator interactions, based its first FIP on the most prominent initiatives for standardising data and metadata on species

⁷⁵ Miller, J., Robertson, T., Wieczorek, J. (2023a), p.4. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849241>

⁷⁶ Miller, J., Robertson, T., Wieczorek, J. (2023a), p.4. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849241>

⁷⁷ Miller, J., Robertson, T., Wieczorek, J. (2023b), p.4. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731625>

⁷⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386484>; FIP Wizard

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/9542ef0d-66d3-4851-b53a-3eaf5ece921c>

⁷⁹ Trekels, M., Pignatari Drucker, D., Salim, J. A., Ollerton, J., Poelen, J., Miranda Soares, F., Rünzel, M., Kasina, M., Groom, Q., Devoto, M. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D10.1) Agriculture-related pollinator data standards use cases report (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8356529>

⁸⁰ Drucker, D. P., Salim, J. A., Poelen, J., Soares, F. M., Gonzalez-Vaquero, R. A., Devoto, M., Ollerton, J., Kasina, M., Carneiro, L. G., Bergamo, P. J., Alves, D. A., Varassin, I., Tinoco, F. C., Rünzel, M., Robinson, D., Cardona-Duque, J., Idárraga, M., Agudelo-Zapata, M. C., Marentes Herrera, E., ... Saraiva, A. (2024). WorldFAIR (D10.3) Agricultural biodiversity FAIR data assessment rubrics (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10719265>

interactions: namely Global Biotic Interactions (GloBI)⁸¹, Darwin Core⁸², Plant-Pollinator Interactions (PPI)⁸³, and GBIF. The WP10 team discovered that “the majority of the FAIR (sub)principles are enabled by at least one of these [four] resources, and that the main challenges are related to consistent adoption and convergence. In other words, there are alternative pathways within the existing resources to enable FAIRness, and there are opportunities to explore and propose specific guidelines to encourage the FAIR standards adoption for plant-pollinator data.”⁸⁴

The insights from these findings were used to develop a FAIR rubric and a data review process tailored to pollination and taxonomic names, with the main focus on encouraging data sharing and reuse. This was further developed and presented in the WorldFAIR ‘Deliverable 10.3 - Agricultural biodiversity FAIR data assessment rubrics’⁸⁵. The FIPs were a useful step towards developing this rubric for good practice in plant-pollinator data. The tool is targeted at data producers and involves translating from IT terminology to terminology more familiar to scientists in the field of plant-pollinator interactions and biodiversity. The rubric includes questions specific to the domain, based on the FIP structure. FIPs were very useful in the sense that they allowed the WP team to understand the core elements of a FAIR data object. The work with FIPs also enabled the WP team to map FAIR resources, such as metadata schemas and ontologies, that can be reused in the domain. Specifically, the rubric is designed “to standardise the review process of datasets on plant-pollinator interactions and to qualitatively assess their reusability. In this assessment tool, we provide a list of 11 rubric items, stated as questions, to facilitate the reuse of plant-pollinator interactions data. Each specific plant-pollinator rubric item is linked to one or more WP10 FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) items [or FERs] and associated FAIR principles or sub-principles.”⁸⁶

The collaboration involved in the WP will continue to update the current FIP⁸⁷ when new FERs relevant to the community are developed. It is anticipated that the community will continue to spend time on improving collaboration workflows such as data peer review protocols to help better understand the context in which the various datasets currently exist, what they contain, who maintains them, and how they can be aligned with other, similar, datasets.

⁸¹ Poelen, J., Simons, J., Mungall, C. (2014) 'Global biotic interactions: An open infrastructure to share and analyze species-interaction datasets', *Ecological Informatics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2014.08.005>

⁸² Wieczorek, J., Bloom, D., Guralnick, R., Blum, S., Döring, M., Giovanni, R., Robertson, T., Vieglais, D. (2012). Darwin core: An evolving community-developed biodiversity data standard. *PLoS ONE*, 7(1), e29715. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0029715>

⁸³ Salim, J. A., Saraiva, A. M., Zermoglio, P. F., Agostini, K., Wolowski, M., Drucker, D. P., Soares, F. M., Bergamo, P. J., Varassin, I. G., Freitas, L., Maués, M. M., Rech, A. R., Veiga, A. K., Acosta, A. L., Araujo, A. C., Nogueira, A., Blochtein, B., Freitas, B. M., Albertini, B. C., ... Brito, V. L. G. (2022). Data standardization of plant–pollinator interactions. *GigaScience*, 11, giac043. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giac043>

⁸⁴ Trekels, M., et al. (2023), p. 11. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8356529>

⁸⁵ Drucker, D. P., et al., (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10719265>

⁸⁶ Drucker, D. P., et al., (2024), p. 8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10719265>

⁸⁷ FIP in FIP Wizard, see: <https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/9542ef0d-66d3-4851-b53a-3eaf5ece921c>

Similarly, the collaboration intends to maintain and use the FIP in our other projects to disseminate knowledge within the community of practice regarding FAIR principles and best practices in the domain. Furthermore, as Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) aligns its current biodiversity standards with FAIR principles,⁸⁸ it is anticipated that the FIP can serve as an important resource for assessing the current state of TDWG standards and identifying areas needing attention and improvement.

3.9 WP11 Ocean Sciences

Completed FIP(s): ODIS knowledge graph, published using JSON-LD/schema.org conventions⁸⁹; deprecated first draft FIP⁹⁰ on ODIS⁹¹.

Account of FIPs experience in reports: D11.1 ‘An assessment of the Ocean Data priority areas for development and implementation’, pp. 16-28 (analysis of other WPs FIPs to identify connections)⁹².

Understanding the planet’s oceans requires expertise from geography in all its forms: biology, physics, chemistry, the social sciences, humanities, and many more domains. Ocean Science is, by definition, a highly multi-disciplinary and multi-domain field. WorldFAIR WP11 used the FIPs produced by the other case studies in an analysis of data practices from the other case studies in order to identify technical points of contact. The FIPs as an exercise, and the information provided in the spreadsheet forms of the FIPs, were useful for identifying “both generic and domain-specific (meta)data exchange conventions and FERs with high potential to bridge other WorldFAIR case studies to and with ODIS (Oceans Data Information System).”⁹³

In this context, the potential benefits of articulating FERs and FIPs is clear: “this information can help identify priority areas for capacity development and/or alignment (e.g. overlapping FAIR Enabling Resources [FERs]), as well as which partners to engage in order to begin merging digital ecosystems across domains. The greatest opportunities lie where concrete, functional implementations of the FAIR Principles are technically similar, are capable of delivering (meta)data in domain-neutral forms, and where there is compatible usage of FERs by a diverse base of practitioners. Consequently, given an overview of a cross-domain digital exchange landscape, any one domain can begin to build and test both multi-domain and bi-domain interoperability

⁸⁸ Vignes Lebbe R (2023) FAIR Principles and TDWG Standards: The case of morphological description of taxa and specimens. Biodiversity Information Science and Standards 7: e111859. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.7.111859>

⁸⁹ <https://github.com/iodepo/odis-in/issues/9>

⁹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386555>; FIP Wizard:

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/2a8ee9b7-be92-4537-8539-5c7469c8bade>

⁹¹ <https://oceaninfohub.org/odis/>

⁹² Buttgeieg, P. L. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D11.1) An assessment of the Ocean Data priority areas for development and implementation roadmap (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682399>

⁹³ Buttgeieg, P.L. (2023), p.14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682399>

approaches.”⁹⁴ The analysis conducted in D11.1 identified a number of points of contact across the case studies: in turn, this was useful to the other work packages and to discussions around CDIF development.

Nevertheless, the Ocean Science Work Package (WP11) notes that the implementation and management of FIPs — as done by through FIP Wizard⁹⁵ and because of the technological commitment to nanopublications — runs counter to the general principles of non-captivity, autonomy, and broad interoperability used to build and operate the ODIS (Ocean Data Information System) Federation. These principles are also featured in Section 4 of D11.2 and will do so in the upcoming zero draft (due in 2024) of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development’s Data and Information Strategy Implementation Plan. Namely, the use of one system to create, manage, and publish FIPs and its bespoke schemata and semantics to embed the FIP questions and answers precludes usage of the FIP Wizard by ODIS. Similarly WP11 was concerned with the specification of the question set (which, it is argued, does not correspond sufficiently to the requirements of the FAIR principles) and the mechanism for encoding the FIPs (nanopublications, a form of RDF with provenance). The FIP Wizard was, of course, an attempt to make it easy for data stewards to create FIPs. It is currently understood that the FAIR Connect platform⁹⁶ will provide an alternative way to register FIPs and FERs. And nanopublications can be ‘minted’ with other tools. Nevertheless, it does seem possible that the platforms and technological underpinnings may pose challenges for uptake and conflict with principles intended to maximise adoption and interoperability, as noted above. The declaration of FERs and FIPs by research communities, data infrastructures, and authoritative organisations is clearly valuable. The use of a more widely adoptable approach based on ubiquitous web technologies would offer a viable alternative. A proposed solution, suggested by WP11, is described in more detail below.

3.10 WP12 Disaster Risk Reduction

Completed FIP(s): DRR FIP⁹⁷ characterising Pacific Data Hub⁹⁸.

Account of FIPs experience in reports: D12.1 ‘Disaster Risk Reduction Case study report’, pp. 20-42 (gap analysis, FAIR assessment and metadata analysis)⁹⁹.

Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) is a diverse area of research that crosses a number of research domains and operational sectors. Although there is awareness of the FAIR principles in the sector, the preoccupation of the organisations on the ground is with capacity building, with making data

⁹⁴ Buttegieg, P.L. (2023), p.8-9. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682399>

⁹⁵ <https://gofair-foundation.github.io/fip/GettingStarted.html>

⁹⁶ <https://fairconnect.pro/>

⁹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386598>; FIP Wizard:

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/05d1c082-6994-4454-bcf3-66340c3fa1f5>

⁹⁸ <https://pacificdata.org/>

⁹⁹ Bolland, J., Fakhruddin, B., Reinen-Hamill, R. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D12.1) Disaster Risk Reduction Case study report (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887557>

available (from analogue to digital format) and with accessing useful remote sensing data. A lot of work is going on to standardise and harmonise terminologies.

Initially, the WorldFAIR DRR case study work package used the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model¹⁰⁰ and other methods to identify gaps in FAIR practice. In part, this was because the wide diversity of data sources and practices in DRR meant that a preliminary indication of whether any FERs were being used seemed more tractable than to list which FERs were being used. It was also important to survey the services provided and to examine the discovery metadata and consider data gaps. For these reasons, the FIPs and notions of FERs played a less important role in the reports of this case study.

Nevertheless, as the notions of FERs and FIPs became better socialised and understood the WP produced a FIP characterising the work of the Pacific Data Hub. This will be an avenue for future work and engagement with the good practice recommendations emerging from WorldFAIR and CDIF.

3.11 WP13 Cultural Heritage

Completed FIP(s): Cultural Heritage FIP¹⁰¹ characterising Digital Repository of Ireland¹⁰².

Account of FIPs experience in reports: D13.1 'Practices and policies supporting Cultural Heritage image sharing platforms', p. 7, p. 12 (arguments for considering focus differently in Cultural Heritage)¹⁰³; D13.2 'Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report', pp. 11-14 (arguments for focusing on a discrete set of FAIR enabling recommendations), pp. 15-25 (recommendations)¹⁰⁴.

The WorldFAIR WP13 case study on cultural heritage research found that the initial FIP exercise was an interesting way to interrogate the technical scope of the Digital Repository of Ireland repository functionality, which has been added onto in *ad hoc* ways over the years (in the sense that someone asks for a feature, and often it is added as a result). Ultimately this made the picture a little unclear in terms of what kinds of connections are supported, how many different ways data can get into and out of the repository, what the limits are of combinations (some things can be deposited using a

¹⁰⁰ Bahim, C., Casorrán-Amilburu, C., Dekkers, M., Herczog, E., Loozen, N., Repanas, K., Russell, K., Stall, S. (2020) 'The FAIR Data Maturity Model: An Approach to Harmonise FAIR Assessments', *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), p. 41.

<https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-041>

¹⁰¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386616>; FIP Wizard:

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/58277f74-4708-4d6a-ade6-d47081b9490a>

¹⁰² <https://dri.ie/>

¹⁰³ Knazook, B., Murphy, J. (2023a). WorldFAIR Project (D13.1) Cultural Heritage Mapping Report: Practices and policies supporting Cultural Heritage image sharing platforms (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7659002>

¹⁰⁴ Knazook, B., Murphy, J., Barner, K., Cassidy, K., Claeysens, S., Cortese, C., Manchester, E. J., Padilla, T., Reijkerker, D., Robson, G., Schmidt, A., Sherratt, T., Warren, M. (2023b). WorldFAIR Project (D13.2) Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897244>

particular technology or standard but not necessarily exported that way), etc. The completed FIP shows all those possibilities.

For the purposes of moving towards FAIR in the cultural heritage and GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) sector, the WP focused on a subset of FAIR-supporting or FAIR-related issues; namely: Citation Model, Transparency, Data Documentation, Licensing and Rights, Delivery. These concepts make sense for prioritising the improvement and greater alignment of such repository services for cultural heritage.

4. Feedback on the FIPs

Having summarised the use of FIPs in each case study, this section characterises feedback on the FIPs methodology.

4.1 What is the utility of FIPs?

In general, the WorldFAIR case studies found the FIPs exercise to be constructive and helpful, both as an activity to stimulate reflection on the FAIR principles and as a means of uncovering gaps in a discipline's practice around FAIR or connections with other disciplines' use of FERs.

4.1.1 Stimulating reflection on FAIR practices and identifying gaps

For some of the case studies, this was a very helpful learning process. The FAIR principles, and the related FIPs and FERs methodology, come with a specific terminology that some characterise as jargon and find off-putting. A number of the WorldFAIR case studies commented that the FIPs exercises enabled them to familiarise themselves with the terminology and get over the apparent barrier this initially created.

All the case studies concur that the FIPs exercises, particularly in the spreadsheet form, were useful for initiating reflection on the FAIR principles, identifying gaps in FAIR practice and links to practice in other disciplines. The methodology is a valuable prompt to operationalising the FAIR principles at a general level in a given research area: particularly helpful in this regard is the classification of FAIR-enabling functionality in the FER typology (that is, the typology of precisely which FAIR sub-principle(s) the FER is used to address) (WP03 - Chemistry). In some case studies it stimulated further reflection on the specific FAIR sub-principles and how to address them (WP10 - Agricultural Biodiversity). The FIPs exercise also enabled i) identification of FAIR-enabling resources and practices that existed before the name (WP05 - Geochemistry¹⁰⁵); and ii) identification of gaps that need to be addressed (WP10).

¹⁰⁵ Prent, A., et al., (2023b). D5.3 Guidelines for implementing Geochemistry FIPs, p10. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10712808>

4.1.2 Reference and model for data stewardship

The utility of an ‘As-Is’ FIP to characterise current practice (and identify gaps), and a reference FIP as a model of good practice, was identified by a number of case studies (WP04 - Nanomaterials, WP05 - Geochemistry, WP10 - Agricultural Biodiversity). Reference FIPs could serve as a guide to improve data stewardship, which in turn would have significant benefits for the discipline (saving time and effort, encouraging data reuse and convergence around FAIR implementation)¹⁰⁶. Reference FIPs could encourage culture change and there could be a significant didactic use for data practitioners, data stewards and researchers¹⁰⁷.

4.1.3 Role in FAIR compliance and assessment

The notion of a reference FIP as a mechanism to encourage good practice and convergence among subdisciplines and across data infrastructures was advanced particularly forcefully by the Geochemistry case study (WP05). They can be a model or reference to encourage compliance: “FIPs are key to understanding which resources or technologies are used to make a defined community's data compliant with the FAIR principles.”¹⁰⁸ This was explored even further in the Agricultural Biodiversity case study (WP10), which developed a rubric to guide data producers and for use in the review of dataset compliance with the FAIR principles.

4.1.4 Identifying commonalities across domains

The FIPs approach, and the discussion of FIPs in the WorldFAIR project, was clearly useful to provide insight into the practices in other domains (WP08 - Urban Health, WP10 - Agricultural Biodiversity). Of particular value was being able to identify the specific use of FERs to identify commonalities or potential convergences. This could have the potential to be useful not just at a global/multi-domain level but also within a domain or even within an organisation (WP08 - Urban Health). It helps learning from the practice in other domains and even benchmarking across domains (WP07 - Population Health).

As noted above, WP11 - Ocean Sciences analysed the FIPs produced across the WorldFAIR case studies in order to identify commonly used FERs, concluding “Each FIP conducted during WorldFAIR has revealed potential routes towards interoperability with ODIS”, and the most viable avenues to

¹⁰⁶ Drucker et al (2024). WorldFAIR (D10.3) Agricultural biodiversity FAIR data assessment rubrics (Version 1), p. 26, Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10719265>

¹⁰⁷ Bilal, U., Ortigoza, A., Li, R., Anderson, T. (2024). WorldFAIR (D8.2) Urban health data - learning and training (Version 1), pp. 46. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731625>

¹⁰⁸ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R. (2024). WorldFAIR (D5.2), p14, Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10406332>

pursue “to establish and sustain cross-domain interoperability.”¹⁰⁹ Other WPs found this analysis to be useful and built upon it.¹¹⁰

In many cases, the commonly-used FERs were unsurprising: widely used, domain-neutral, identifier schemes like ORCID, DOI, and ROR figure strongly. Similarly, identifiers or classifications like IGSN and InChI are present in a number of related case studies. However, in a number of instances, the FIP-enabled comparison across domains, allied with further discussions, stimulated the adoption of (or intention to adopt) specific FERs. For example, “the long-term goal of SALURBAL (WP08 - Urban Health) is to be integrated into the larger global FAIR ecosystem, specifically by adopting the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) Standards.”¹¹¹ The second WP08 FIP illustrates in detail how the use of DDI standards, and related tools, will help address the FAIR sub-principles in relation to Interoperability and Reusability

Similarly, the FIPs exercise highlighted the commonalities between the WP07 (Population Health) approach (using the OHSDI Common Data Model alongside schema.org/JSON-LD for publishing rich metadata in a machine-readable manner) with the ODIS recommendations discussed in WP11 (Ocean Sciences). By highlighting such commonalities, the FIP can help reveal a common ‘starting-block’ for interoperability, and alignment across domains (WP07 - Population Health). Accordingly, this approach was incorporated into the draft CDIF recommendations for discovery.¹¹²

Initiated by the FIPs exercise, a further detailed analysis of the use of FERs can be enlightening as the first step to detailed mapping across domains or subdomains: “Comparing FIPs associated with the same or different levels of data granularity can be beneficial. This comparison can help to identify overlapping, redundant or different usages of FERs in use for data FAIRification. This can highlight where there are differences between FERs (e.g., metadata profiles, vocabularies, ontologies, formats), and define where crosswalks need to be developed and published, or other techniques utilised to enable interoperability (e.g., SSSOM – Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings; Matentzoglou et al., 2022).”¹¹³

¹⁰⁹ Buttegieg, P. L. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D11.1) An assessment of the Ocean Data priority areas for development and implementation roadmap (Version 1), p. 24, p. 35. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682399>

¹¹⁰ E.g. Lynch, I., Afantitis, A., Exner, T., Papadiamantis, A. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D4.1) Nanomaterials domain-specific FAIRification mapping (Version 1), p. 43. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887341>

¹¹¹ Bilal, U., Ortigoza, A., Li, R., Anderson, T. (2024). WorldFAIR (D8.2) Urban health data - learning and training (Version 1), pp. 44-45. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731625>

¹¹² Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) Working Group, Richard, S., Gregory, A., Hodson, S., Fils, D., Kanjala, C., Bell, D., Winstanley, P., Edwards, M., Heus, P., Brickley, D., Rizzolo, F., Maxwell, L., Luis, G., Buttigieg, P. L., Le Franc, Y. (2023). Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF): Discovery Module (v01 draft for public consultation) (Version 01). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252564>

¹¹³ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R. (2024a). WorldFAIR (D5.2) Geochemistry Methodology and Outreach, p. 22 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10406332>

4.2 Discussion of how best to use FIPs

While the potential utility of FIPs is clear, there remain important points to clarify about how best to use them. These points pertain to the level and granularity of use, and the intended users.

4.2.1 Level of use: domain, community, repository, dataset?

Already considered in WorldFAIR D2.1 ‘FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: What Have We Learnt?’¹¹⁴, the level at which a FIP might best be compiled was a subject of much uncertainty and discussion. It is clear that in a research field like Disaster Risk Reduction, where so many varied data types are at play, it seems difficult to know where to start. A FIP of remote sensing data would be very different to a FIP of municipal assets data, or loss data, or geophysical data, etc. The challenge and the task seem enormous! Where do we start?

Nevertheless, case studies did find it useful to break down the problem space and use FIPs at finer levels of granularity. For WP07, it was evident that a FIP at the level of the ‘population health’ discipline, or even one that tried to characterise a multi-project, multi-database initiative like INSPIRE would have little utility. Here, the most pertinent unit would be the study and its attendant database. The FIP could be a mechanism to encourage a degree of technical and semantic alignment between studies. However, as some technical solutions are developed ‘on the fly’ for the needs of a particular study or analysis, the FIP may often need to be an *ex post facto* summary (WP07 - Population Health).

In response to similar considerations, WP05 (Geochemistry) advocated the use of FIPs at multiple levels. “To facilitate machine-to-machine readability of data in geochemistry, FIPs [should] be generated and associated with various data levels: 1) dataset, 2) data collection and 3) data repository. Associating a FIP to those three levels of (aggregated) data makes it clear to data users and contributors what resources were chosen to make that data FAIR. Further interoperability at the appropriate level can then be achieved by the adoption or mapping of FERs.”¹¹⁵ The case study also suggested that a fourth tier would be useful: “the disciplinary / synthesis database. From fine to coarse, the four data granularity levels defined here are dataset, data collection, disciplinary/synthesis database, repository.”¹¹⁶

This analysis and listing of FERs can provide the basis for establishing mappings and interoperability at the levels required, and ultimately at the level of the discipline. Fundamentally, a FIP can be used to describe precisely what resources were used to enable each FAIR principle. However, the number of FERs required increases with the complexity of a data collection or data repository, and FIPs that apply to a coarser level of data granularity (e.g. repository) will note more FERs per FAIR Principle

¹¹⁴ Gregory, A., Hodson, S. (2022), pp.18-19. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378109>

¹¹⁵ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R. (2024). WorldFAIR (D5.2), p14 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10406332>

¹¹⁶ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R. (2024). WorldFAIR (D5.2), p22 p.15; pp.15-19 for further definitions and discussion. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10406332>

unless all the data of finer granularity in that coarse level is completely standardised following a single set of FERs. It is therefore beneficial for users of data publishing infrastructure to publish a FIP that applies to a particular data granularity level when making data available, in order to enable interoperability across different granularity levels of data between different communities. The availability of a FIP with the appropriate data granularity level then facilitates interoperability and convergence. It is important that each FIP has a DOI [or other persistent identifier]¹¹⁷ and is version-controlled and linked to the relevant dataset/data collection as a Related Identifier.

“The availability of FIPs and their generation serves a dual purpose: it informs data consumers on the implementation choices and resources used to make data FAIR, and it guides data-producing communities on identifying and creating missing resources to enhance data FAIRness.”¹¹⁸

The Geochemistry case study (WP05) presents an enticing vision of a community approach to publishing FIPs and FERs that would work at multiple levels and enable interoperability within a broad discipline as well as with other disciplines. This approach would leverage a geochemistry website, or information resource, that follows the example of the Ocean Best Practices System website¹¹⁹. It would be a place where “FERs from the reference FIP and other resources can be published, promulgated and updated by the relevant local, regional, international and global communities.”¹²⁰ The vision for how to achieve this in Geochemistry is presented in a series of recommendations in successive reports (WorldFAIR D5.2 and D5.3) and are worth considering for other disciplines.

Nevertheless, implementing this vision would raise a number of issues in relation to FIPs and FERs which will be explored below: namely, the role of (authoritative) organisations publishing FIPs and (above all) FERs; the need for a critical mass of adoption; and the way in which FIPs and FERs are encoded.

4.3 What must be improved in the FIPs approach?

Recognising the general value of the approach and the hard work and commitment of the GO FAIR colleagues that had developed the methodology, the WorldFAIR case studies nevertheless identified a number of areas in which the FIPs approach could be improved relating to the usability, development and sustainability of the FIP Wizard and infrastructures.

The most frequent observations relate to the usability of the FIP Wizard tool. The need to come to terms with some of the FAIR-related terminology has been remarked on above. While most WPs

¹¹⁷ As nanopublication, the FIPs and FERs are currently provided with a ‘trusty URI’. These are created using a hash of the nanopublication. Although these fulfil requirements, and have advantages, they are less familiar to many colleagues. Kuhn, T., Dumontier, M. (2014). Trusty URIs: Verifiable, immutable, and permanent digital artifacts for linked data. arXiv:1401.5775v3 <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1401.5775>

¹¹⁸ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R. (2024a). WorldFAIR (D5.2), p. 19. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1040633>

¹¹⁹ <https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/>

¹²⁰ Prent, A., et al., 2023b. D5.3, p. 12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10712808>

found the questionnaire-based exercises straightforward, some had difficulties with the online tool. A number reported that the user interface of the FIP Wizard was not very intuitive to use. While it is understandable that ‘guardrail’ features are present to orient users and ensure the data entry is as FAIR or correct as possible, the excess use of guardrails crowd the UI and make it less accessible, meaning that it takes longer for groups to enter their information correctly. Completing the information in the Wizard was time-intensive, with or without prior preparation by means of a spreadsheet. Any way in which the very manual assertion process can be improved would be welcome (WP08 - Urban Health).

Particularly important is the lack of an analytic or visualisation dimension. The current FIP Wizard only supports data entry and does not provide many analytic features into the data being collected. For example, users are not able to visualise the result of their own or other FIPs. It would be a considerable improvement if users were able to view the convergence matrix of other FIPs within the same domain. Adding such analytic features will incentivise users to spend time to input their FIP, as they know they will get something out of it (WP08 - Urban Health). In general it was clear that a number of WPs found the spreadsheet-based exercises enlightening and enjoyable, but found completing the survey in the FIPs Wizard very time-consuming, and a task for which they could summon little enthusiasm.

As FIPs are encoded as nanopublications, it can be argued that creating visualisations of FIPs, or networks of FIPs, is as easy or hard as any other flavour of RDF. Some scripts have been made available¹²¹. Not all the case studies in WorldFAIR, or the scientific communities they represent, can necessarily draw on the skills to use such scripts, or prioritise such work. Perhaps overestimating the maturity of the system, many colleagues understandably expected to be able to easily visualise the results of their quite laborious data entry. As has been remarked by the GO FAIR team themselves, the best current visuals of a FIPs graph are still those produced by Kristine Hettne in 2019¹²². The GO FAIR team argue this is due to insufficient funding. Others in the WorldFAIR community argue that a more widely-used technological underpinning, such as JSON-LD, would allow the engagement of a wider developer community. Approaches to using different syntax representations of FIPs will require more exploration to resolve this issue.

The issue of resourcing is related to the development arc of tools and easy means for visualisation, but it also raises the issue of sustainability of the FIP Wizard and its supporting infrastructure. In many respects, the progress made since the inception of the FAIR convergence matrix idea at the GO FAIR Implementation Networks meeting in January 2019 has been remarkable, and the hard work and dedication of the GO FAIR team should be recognised¹²³. It was not in scope for the WorldFAIR project to scrutinise in detail the sustainability plans for the FIP Wizard and related infrastructures, but those case studies that could envisage important uses for the FIPs approach in

¹²¹ See <https://github.com/eu-parc/FAIR-convergence-matrix> and <https://gist.github.com/10/32088aef3b16b216e349212af20de418>

¹²² <https://osf.io/a3pgk/>

¹²³ Gregory, A., Hodson, S. (2022), WorldFAIR D2.1, p.8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378109>

their communities (notably WP05 - Geochemistry and WP10 - Agricultural Biodiversity) naturally raised the question. It will be important to review and plan for sustainability of the FIP Wizard software and its hosting, and the dependencies on the nanopublication server network. One avenue being explored is FAIR Connect¹²⁴, which is supported by a not-for-profit foundation in which GO FAIR, IOS Press and CODATA are represented on the advisory board. This and other avenues to sustain the infrastructure will need to be explored and reviewed.

4.3.1 Encoding of FERs and Nanopublications

The means and the ways in which FERs are encoded potentially creates usability issues as well as more general concerns. The system is based on ‘nanopublications’, a form of RDF including basic provenance information about the ‘assertion’¹²⁵. Nanopublications are intended to be a ‘permanent’ record of an ‘assertion’. This means that in the nanopublications server network they are not deleted: rather a faulty record can be ‘deprecated’. A resource description can be updated, and when this happens the new record supersedes the old one. In order to be used in the FIP Wizard for the creation of FIPs, FERs need to be ‘minted’ or published. (A number of users found the jargon term ‘minting a nanopublication’ non-evident). Until this is done, the FER will not appear in the FIP Wizard dropdown lists. When entering the information relating to an FER, the user needs to indicate which function the FER performs, that is in relation to which FAIR sub-principle it is an FER. A single FER actually can have multiple functions and can address numerous FAIR sub-principles. This is accommodated in the system, but if the user omits one of these functions at the moment of creation then, the FER will not appear in the relevant dropdown list. The FER needs to be updated with the additional information. A number of users found this process confusing.

4.3.2 Role of sponsoring or authoritative organisations

To realise the admirable and important vision of FIPs contributing to FAIR convergence, there needs to be a critical mass of information accessible to users; and it needs to be easy to visualise the FIPs, and to explore which FERs are being used. Understandably, descriptions of FERs have been created in the system without the involvement of the organisations responsible for those FERs, resulting in substandard and unendorsed definitions and descriptions of the FERs in question. In a proof of concept, this is acceptable, but if the FIPs approach is to provide the information necessary to advance FAIR practices and enable convergence around FERs, then this needs to be addressed. The profiles and descriptions of FERs should be verified with the sponsoring organisations to ensure that the information reflects reality for the benefit of the community considering to implement these (WP03).

¹²⁴ <https://fairconnect.pro/>

¹²⁵ <https://nanopub.net/>

Fundamentally, these are socio-technical challenges: how to socialise the creation of FERs and FIPs in the community and how to ensure the connections to responsible organisations that are necessary to maintain the quality of information (about FERs).

One of the potential strengths of the use of nanopublications is precisely the inclusion of the authorial provenance in the FER or FIP graph. Nevertheless, some of the ‘authoritative’ organisations involved in WorldFAIR asked, ‘why should we not publish IUPAC FERs and FIPs so they are available, in the easiest form we can use?’ They also expressed concern when finding FERs relating to their standards, which had been created by FIP users but did not conform to the accepted definition and description of the standard.

At the same time, possibly the most significant conceptual advantage of nanopublications is that they wrap a set of statements in a specific structure and provide authorial provenance. This could be of benefit to those authoritative organisations or communities, who wish to assert with clarity and traceability what standards or specifications are recommended in a given community.

FIPs are graphs that link the FAIR sub-principles to ways of addressing them (FERs). Ultimately, then, the success of the FIPs approach as a socio-technical solution rests heavily on FERs being well-characterised in the system, or in a place where they are referenced in a FIP. The FAIRsharing¹²⁶ resource now lists many ‘FERs’ (described as “terminology artefacts, models/formats, reporting guidelines, and identifier schemas”) and many of these entries are ‘maintained’ by people with connections to the responsible organisations.¹²⁷

Naturally enough, a number of WorldFAIR Case Studies suggested that it would be useful to have greater integration between FAIRsharing and the FIPs platform: this would allow the considerable number of FERs in FAIRsharing to be referenced in FIPs. A mechanism already exists to allow FER nanopublications to be created that include a FAIRsharing PID (DOI) in the resource information, thereby adding the link to the FAIRsharing entry.¹²⁸ These FERs are then automatically marked with a FAIRsharing logo in the FIPs Wizard. Currently, this is often done as part of the qualification process conducted by GO FAIR Foundation facilitators because there is not a specific prompt in the FIP Wizard (though that could easily be added). Adding the FAIRsharing link has to be done ‘manually’ on an individual basis. Most fundamentally, there is currently no mechanism for a wholesale import and transformation of the FAIRsharing metadata into the nanopublication structure, although this should in principle be technically possible. Being able to include all the FAIRsharing resources as FERs in such a way that they can be referenced in FIPs would greatly improve the power of both resources. Therefore, it would seem a priority to develop and

¹²⁶ <https://fairsharing.org/>

¹²⁷ <https://fairsharing.org/FAIRsharing.ddk9t9> (InChI) and <https://fairsharing.org/FAIRsharing.1t5ws6> (DDI Lifecycle).

¹²⁸ Template:

<https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/projects/create?selectedProjectTemplate=ffe20c8c-258d-4767-8ea7-3f8aadd07f02>

implement a mechanism such that the information about FERs already available in FAIRsharing can help power the FIPs approach.

Achieving the success of the FIPs vision will require a critical mass of information and for FIPs to be available for analysis and visualisation. If the information is declared, it should be relatively easy to create graphs or maps of how FERs are implemented: by which organisation, for what FAIR functionality and how. Such maps would need to be interactive and provide options for both visual interrogation and programmatic implementation into services where this information can be exploited. The benefits of such information would be considerable, and this is the real insight and appeal of the FIP vision. The GO FAIR team is naturally aware of these requirements and some visualisation and/or analytical tools are available on the FAIRconnect site.¹²⁹ Nevertheless, it may still be the case that the labour required to create FIPs and FERs, the wish to organise this only through the FAIR Connect portal, and the commitment to nanopublications retards progress of what could be a vibrant community resource. Addressing these issues is an important aspect of making FIPs and FERs a mature tool for the FAIR community broadly, but it is recognised that this demands a sufficient investment in further developing and integrating the needed software, and in refining and optimising the technology approaches.

In summary, for the FIPs vision to be realised, FERs need to be published and updated by responsible or authoritative organisations. A considerable number of organisations (particularly repositories) or other organisations that represent practice would need to publish FIPs (along the lines outlined by WP05 above). And most importantly, for this to be achieved, it will be essential to find ways of lowering the barrier to information entry and improving the way in which FIPs and FERs can be easily visualised and analysed.

4.4 An alternative to nanopublications for FIPs?

One alternative for how a FIP might be encoded, has been suggested by the Ocean Sciences WP11, in response to the issues described above.

4.4.1 An ODIS FIP using JSON-LD/schema.org

As a solution, ODIS is implementing what it argues is a more open and broadly interoperable serialisation and semantic markup of its FIP, leveraging the JSON-LD/schema.org conventions noted in D11.1 and D11.2. This file is version controlled in GitHub, allowing normative tracking of its evolution through time. A PID for this JSON-LD file will be issued once the document has been reviewed. Progress to this end is being tracked on the *odis-arch* issue tracker¹³⁰. In essence, a metadata record about the ODIS Knowledge Graph, generated and maintained by the International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange (IODE), is being created.

¹²⁹ <http://v2.fairconnect.pro/dashboard>

¹³⁰ <https://github.com/iodepo/odis-in/issues/9> - associated with pull request

An excerpt of this record is embedded below.

```
{
  "@context": {
    "@vocab": "https://schema.org/"
  },
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "@id": "URL: Optional. A URL that resolves to *this* JSON-LD document, NOT
the URL of the CreativeWork that this JSON-LD document describes. To link to
the CreativeWork itself, please use 'url' and/or 'identifier'",
  "name": "The Ocean Data and Information System (ODIS) Knowledge Graph",
  "version": "{odis-kg-version}",
  "alternateName": "The ODIS KG.",
  "description": "The Ocean Data and Information System (ODIS) Knowledge Graph
is the synthesis of (meta)data catalogues shared by the partners of the ODIS
Federation. These files are harvested and merged to create a collective
knowledge base of the ODIS Federation's digital holdings. These products are
maintained and released by the IODE of IOC-UNESCO.",
  "url": "https://odis.org",
  "about": "The Ocean Data and Information System (ODIS) Federation",
  "abstract": "The Ocean Data and Information System (ODIS) Knowledge Graph is
the synthesis of (meta)data catalogues shared by the partners of the ODIS
Federation. These files are harvested and merged to create a collective
knowledge base of the ODIS Federation's digital holdings. These products are
maintained and released by the IODE of IOC-UNESCO.",
  "accessMode": [
    "textual",
    "visual"
  ],
  ...
}
```

Within this JSON-LD/schema.org record, the questions associated with the FIPs have been embedded using the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) Ontology¹³¹ (as used by the FIP Wizard, offering an avenue for interoperation). An excerpt is provided below. The other classes in the FIP Ontology are not used, as either 1) schema.org offers far more broadly useful equivalents which

¹³¹ <https://peta-pico.github.io/FAIR-nanopubs/fip/index-en.html>

bespoke systems such as nanopublications should support, or 2) they can be inferred from the semantics present in the ODIS FIP, as it uses the question-answer pattern using FIP terms for questions (assuming the FIP Ontology's axiomatisation is fit for purpose).

In the excerpt below, one will note that the `acceptedAnswer` values are variables such as `{odis-Q-A1-1-D}`. As described and tracked in the ODIS issue tracker, these will be replaced by values derived from periodic queries of the ODIS Knowledge Graph to give more complete and objective assessments of its implementation profile than can be done by a human. This will also greatly reduce the overheads of maintaining the ODIS FIP and dovetail its generation with its native diagnostic routines.

```
...  
  
"potentialAction": [  
  {  
    "@type": "AskAction",  
    "agent": {  
      "@type": "ResearchProject",  
      "name": "Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice",  
      "alternateName": "The WorldFAIR Project",  
      "url": "https://worldfair-project.eu/",  
      "identifier": "https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058393"  
    },  
    "recipient": {  
      "@type": "Organization",  
      "name": "The International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange",  
      "url": "https://www.iode.org",  
      "identifier": "https://oceanexpert.org/institution/10171"  
    },  
    "question": [  
      {  
        "@type": "Question",  
        "text": "Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?",  
        "identifier": "https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/FIP-Question-A1.1-D",  
        "acceptedAnswer": "{odis-Q-A1-1-D}"  
      },  
      {  
        "@type": "Question",  
        "text": "Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata
```

```
records?",  
  "identifier": "https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/FIP-Question-A1.1-MD",  
  "acceptedAnswer": "{odis-Q-A1.1-MD}"  
},
```

WP11 does not believe that all of the FIP questions actually address the FAIR Principle or sub-Principle they claim to. “In some cases, we will answer these questions nonetheless, adding a comment to the JSON-LD stanza noting any issues we have detected. Further, we may add additional questions that we believe to be more germane to FAIR Implementation.” (WP11 - Ocean Sciences). This type of annotation could help in establishing an agreed interpretation of how best to realise the sense of specific FAIR sub-principles.

Likewise, WP11 argues that it would be beneficial for the GO FAIR FIP Wizard to support the export and import of FIPs in such a form to increase its own FAIRness, rather than requiring the use of specialised conventions that few systems in the world will be able to natively process (as opposed to the tens of millions of machines capable of interpreting JSON-LD/schema.org).

It was noted in a number of the WorldFAIR FIPs-related workshops and discussions, including by WP11 (Ocean Sciences) and others, and during the generation of the WorldFAIR FIP Convergence Matrix¹³², that it is necessary to make a distinction between “No declaration made by the community”¹³³ on the basis of lack of maturity or information; and instances where the community feels that no declaration is needed - e.g., where something is Not Applicable - (meta)data shared do not require authorisation / authentication.

In the JSON-LD/schema.org serialisation being implemented by WP11 and ODIS, the ODIS team felt that they are capable of doing this without reliance on the nanopublication system, and are thus better able to align with their principles and those of the free and open Internet. This distinction would also enable truer comparisons of the maturity and convergence between and across domains, as the distinctions of “not sure yet” versus “certain that no FER is needed” would be visualised and evidenced.

4.4.2 WP11’s case for the benefits of the ODIS FIP approach

WP11 argues therefore, that the ODIS implementation and autonomous, open management of its FIP — and its integration into the ODIS diagnostic suite — has enhanced its sustainability. It is likely that answers to most of the FIP questions can be automatically generated either at regular time intervals (weekly, monthly) or with each release of the ODIS Knowledge Graph. With little to no

¹³² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11397305>

¹³³ <https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/FIP-No-Choice-Declaration>

overhead, or reliance on another system, the community can thus generate a broadly interoperable rendition of its FIP in perpetuity.

Further, WP11 maintains that the queries that power the auto-population of the FIP questions in the ODIS FIP will be open and modifiable by external users in other domains. Should they, for example, wish to subset the result set of any query to only those results that feature certain keywords (e.g. “biodiversity”, “archaeology”, etc.), this may be done with a simple modification to the generalised reporting queries. Should other domains, or the FIP Wizard, encode/export their FIPs in alignment to the ODIS use of JSON-LD/schema.org, it then becomes trivial for a broad range of developers (who need not have any familiarity of ODIS itself) to perform cross-domain analysis of FIPs, finding overlaps, gaps, differences, and other properties.

A number of the WorldFAIR WPs were interested in WP11’s arguments and it will be important to consider the pros and cons. By the same token, there has clearly been progress with the GO FAIR vision, the FIPs Wizard and FAIR Connect. It will be important, therefore, to explore whether there is a way of aligning the ODIS and GO FAIR approaches.

5. Next steps: global graph of FERs and FIPs?

The experience of the WorldFAIR project was that the FIPs exercises were enlightening and useful, both for the case studies and the cross-project synthesis work. The project identified a number of highly beneficial uses for FIPs: as didactic tools (e.g. WP08 (Urban Health), WP10 (Agricultural Biodiversity)); as a useful mechanism for normative declarations of good practice (e.g. WP03 (Chemistry), WP04 (Nanomaterials), WP05 (Geochemistry), WP10 (Agricultural Biodiversity)); as a basis for targeted and detailed, domain-specific FAIR assessment (e.g. WP10); and as a mechanism for identifying commonalities across disciplines and cross-domain solutions (e.g. WP11 (Ocean Sciences), WP02 (Synthesis)). Consequently, the WorldFAIR project is strongly supportive of the FIPs approach. As hinted at by the recommendations of WP05 (Geochemistry) and WP11 (Ocean Science), a global graph of FERs and FIPs could be a resource of considerable power and benefit.

The WorldFAIR project identified a number of current barriers to achieving this, which have been articulated above. These include the effort required to create FERs and FIPs (including usability of the FIPs Wizard) and ease of visualisation (which would provide more immediate value and sense of reward for the process). It has been argued these these barriers could be (at least partly) overcome by the wholesale integration of FER information from FAIRsharing and a change in the technical underpinnings (adopting a JSON-LD/schema.org rather than, or in addition to, nanopublications for the encoding of FERs and FIPs).

As noted above, the FIP Wizard will doubtless be a useful tool for many data stewards, but it should not be the only way of declaring and publishing FERs and FIPs. To accelerate progress towards achieving the FIPs vision it would be hugely beneficial to find a mechanism for the wholesale

integration of FAIRsharing entries as FERs that can be identified in FIPs. Is such a solution organisationally and technically possible? It should certainly be explored.

It is suggested that a shift to JSON-LD/schema.org would provide technological underpinnings that better allow the creation of tools to analyse and visualise FIPs, facilitating the engagement of a wider developer base. Based on a widely used web format, it would also be easier to harvest declared FIPs and FERs for this purpose, meeting the aspirations described by WP05 (Geochemistry).

However, there may be a number of challenges to the JSON-LD/schema.org approach. Not all organisations currently have the technical knowledge or the infrastructure to take the approach proposed by ODIS, so the FIPs Wizard - despite some shortcomings - will remain a valuable tool for data stewards. The ODIS proposal argues that the gain in uptake and breadth of use means a JSON-LD/schema.org approach would be beneficial. The GO FAIR Foundation team argues that this would result in semantic loss (particularly in relation to the provenance of the statement and the way in which the nanopublication wraps the set of declarations in FERs and FIPs). Is it possible to find a way of harmonising the nanopublication approach favoured by GO FAIR with the JSON-LD/schema.org approach suggested above? Some of this may be to do with harmonising the object properties in the nanopublication schema with those in schema.org.

The WorldFAIR project recommends that effort is dedicated to aligning and harmonising these approaches in order to enable the FAIR community and the multitude of disciplines to achieve the objectives of the FIPs approach and vision: better understanding current practice, encouraging implementation of the FAIR Principles, providing examples of good practice, and encouraging convergence around commonly used FERs. One of the conclusions of the WorldFAIR project and its case studies is to recommend that such a solution is explored.

With a view to achieving the global graph of FERs and FIPs, and in order to further increase their utility, there are some other ways in which the information in FIPs might be enhanced.

6. Information in FERs and FIPs

The RDA 'FAIR Data Maturity Model Specification and Guidelines'¹³⁴ is a useful introduction and guide to data stewards on considerations in relation to the FAIR principles. Nevertheless, the WorldFAIR project contends that the question set in the FAIR implementation profiles goes a step further, and is more useful. This is because, rather than asking *whether* the repository or dataset uses (for example) a FAIR compliant vocabulary, the FIPs question set asks the user to specify *which*

¹³⁴ Bahim, C., Casorrán-Amilburu, C., Dekkers, M., Herczog, E., Loozen, N., Repanas, K., Russell, K. Stall, S. (2020) 'The FAIR Data Maturity Model: An Approach to Harmonise FAIR Assessments', Data Science Journal, 19(1), p. 41. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-041> and FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

vocabulary (or other FER) is being used. This is an important and necessary step forward in utility and ambition.¹³⁵

Nevertheless, a number of the WorldFAIR case studies suggested that more information could usefully be captured in the FERs. As noted in a number of the case studies above, the FIPs exercise was found to be useful to engage with the FAIR principles and to identify FERs, but the ‘real’, practical work of engineering interoperability and data combination for the purposes of research happens at a level of detail below this (WP03 (Chemistry), WP06 (Social Surveys), WP07 (Population Health), WP08 (Urban Health)). This led to suggestions that a further layer of information and attributes might be needed in the descriptions of FERs and FER types.

For FERs in common use, further delving into implementation considerations may provide indicators of best practices, limitations that need improvement, or where more explicit adoption support may be needed. For example, profiling a critical mass of FERs and their use in a domain could provide useful information (in addition to the mere fact that FER ‘X’ *is* used) about **how** FER ‘X’ is used. This information can then inform guidance and further encourage convergence or normalisation of implementation (WP03 (Chemistry)). This would at least be a natural progression: from **whether** an implementation uses an FER, to declarations of **which** FER is used, to providing further information on precisely **how** the FER is implemented. This is an important dimension for data and metadata validation, which - it can be argued - is an important requirement missing from the FAIR principles.¹³⁶ This perhaps goes beyond the original vision of FERs and is asking a lot at the current state of development, but could be extremely useful as communities develop their FIPs and FERs information. For example, in time, if CDIF plays the role envisaged, it will be useful for FIPs to make specific reference to how the CDIF recommendations and profiles are implemented.

6.1 Data provenance, processing and lineage

The FAIR principles have had a remarkable influence and have greatly assisted progress in data stewardship. Quite rightly, then, the question set in the FIP is based on the FAIR principles. Nevertheless, there are considerations for data and metadata stewardship - particularly in relation to reuse - that are not sufficiently covered. Most notably, the FAIR principles themselves do not sufficiently deal with tracking provenance, processing and ‘data lineage’, which is essential information to support Reusability of data in a scientific context, and in the context of data harmonisation and integration. This is remarked on by the WP08 (Urban Health) case study: “One of the key aspects of the FIP [that should be developed] further is data provenance infrastructure — or tracking meta(data) as it goes through layers of transformation. There are industry workflows such

¹³⁵ And it is itself in line with the FAIR principles: I-3 suggests qualified references to other metadata, and in this case, the metadata refers to the vocabulary used so that a machine re-user can follow that reference.

¹³⁶ See for example, the RIPE (Reliability, Interpretability, Processability and Exchangeability) principles, D3.1, pp.35-42; and Helliwell JR. (2019). FACT and FAIR with Big Data allows objectivity in science: The view of crystallography. Struct Dyn. Oct 25;6(5):054306. doi: 10.1063/1.5124439. PMID: 31673568; PMCID: PMC6816445, on the importance of validation in crystallography.

as Data Built Tools (DBT) to build well-organised data warehouses but these are not commonly utilised in academic settings. In the future, we hope to explore the integration feasibility between the data provenance systems (e.g., DBT) and a FAIR meta(data) inventory.”¹³⁷ Such aspirations apply to any domain where data harmonisation and integration play an important role, in particular the three social science and health oriented case studies.

7. Analysis of the WorldFAIR FIPs

There are numerous ways in which FIPs can be analysed to furnish information about FAIR-related practice in research domains. The most useful activity for WorldFAIR’s purposes included hands-on discussions during the FIPs workshops followed by the sort of analysis undertaken by WP11 - Oceanography in the D11.1 deliverable. In addition to this, as input to work towards the CDIF, the WPO2 - Coordination and Synthesis team held online workshops with each case study to understand their FIPs, and other features of FAIR practice in relation to data and metadata.

Additionally, the information in FIPs lends itself to two primary types of ‘visualisation’ and analysis, namely 1. Creating a matrix; and 2. Plotting relationships.

The first type involves constructing what the GO FAIR Foundation have been referring to as a ‘convergence matrix’ - in essence, a large spreadsheet of FIPs information. Separately, the WorldFAIR matrix¹³⁸ was constructed by Iseult Lynch (WPO4 - Nanomaterials) and contains information from all the case studies’ FIPs (either from the FIP Wizard versions or from the FIP mini questionnaire versions, which were then formalised into the FIP Wizard). The FERs were listed in the order they were added to the sub-principle initially, and then reorganised to appear alphabetically within each sub-principle (for ease of searching), or from most to least used (across WorldFAIR case studies) to visualise those FERs that have cross-domain relevance which could be utilised by other communities / case studies and those that are currently very domain-specific.

An important caveat, of course, is that the different WorldFAIR case studies took different approaches to developing their FIPs, with some being broad to cover a research area and others being very focussed on a specific data platform or standard used by (part) of the community, which is reflected in the fact that some of the FIPs have >50 FERs declared while others have <20 FERs declared, as shown also in Table 1.

We also note in Table 1 that there is no way currently to distinguish between ‘no FERs needed for the sub-principle in a specific domain’ versus ‘the community is not yet able to determine what FER(s) are needed / available’. Table 1 includes all FERs whether currently in use or planned to be

¹³⁷D Bilal, U., Ortigoza, A., Li, R., Anderson, T. (2024). WorldFAIR (D8.2) Urban health data - learning and training (Version 1) p.44. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731625>

¹³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11397305>

used, but the Excel version of the convergence matrix in Zenodo¹³⁹ shows the data for the currently used FERs only.

The matrix affirms the findings of the workshops and consultations. Unsurprisingly, most ‘convergence’ is around the domain-agnostic standards that perform important, fundamental functions for Findability and Reusability (DOIs, ORCIDs and CC licences of various flavours), as well as common web-protocols for Accessing data and metadata (HTTP(S) and REST). Perhaps more notable was the relatively high count for the use of JSON-LD as the ‘knowledge representation language’ (FAIR Principle, Interoperability 1) for both data and metadata, affirming observations drawn from discussions with WP11 - Ocean Sciences, and WP07 - Population Health.

Relatedly, we identified some usage of cross-domain standards recommended in CDIF profiles (schema.org for various functions, SKOS and OWL, PROV-O). If the overall impression remains one of substantial diversity, the WorldFAIR FIPs and the matrix (if maintained as a living resource) will provide valuable insight to the evolution of practice in these disciplines.

The second form of ‘visualisation’ consists in plotting various parts of the ‘graphs’ created by the relationships within and across the WorldFAIR FIPs. This allows us to present a number of aspects of these relationships in a very useful visual way. For example: the most common links across particular clusters of case studies, which FERs are used in common by a number of case studies and so on. In what follows we present a number of examples of these graph visualisations (see figures 2 - 4) which were prepared by Jill Bolland, WP12 - Disaster Risk Reduction, using the matrix data¹⁴⁰.

Initially, it had been envisaged that the case study work packages would develop an initial FIP, and then update it towards the end of the WorldFAIR project, such that we could see the evolution of the FIPs over the project lifetime. In practice, the evolution was continuously ongoing as case studies learned from one another, and gained a deeper understanding of what FIPs are and how they can be used to support the case study research domains. Accordingly, most of the Case Studies continued to evolve their FIPs through the period, rather than having ‘initial’ and ‘final’ versions. This is actually a strength of the tool: that it is a living document that reflects the evolving nature of research fields, and allows it to be updated in real-time. The FIP Wizard can be used to look at the history and see what was added when, but by allowing communities to check back on a FIP’s evolution, but without the need to retire earlier versions (unless of course the community wants to, in which case the option is there).

We note that the end-date aspect of the FIP would actually be more useful as a “valid until” date at which point the FIP should be reviewed by the community to ensure that it remains current, or be updated, and a new validity date added. This would better reflect the “living” nature of the FIPs and

¹³⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11397305>

¹⁴⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11397305>

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increase confidence in users that were not part of the original FIP development but want to implement it in part or whole for their research or research infrastructures.

Another important reflection from the visualisation activities is that at the moment, FIPs do not have a way of indicating how often a specific declared FER is used by the community (i.e., if it's used by everyone as part of their everyday data management workflows or by just a small portion of the community - for example, the early adopters or the modelling experts but not the data generators) and thus there is no way of tracking this over time. Tracking uptake or usage of a declared FER would of course be an incredibly useful functionality to track shifts of usage in a research area and could also be used to demonstrate to tool developers and authoritative organisations the value of declaring their FERs and embedding them into community FIPs as a means to drive uptake and adoption. This is another type of convergence that FIPs have the potential to be able to visualise should improved visualisation tools be made available.

Table 1: Illustration of the number of FERs per FAIR sub-principle declared as ‘in use’ or ‘planned for use’ in the WorldFAIR case studies. The full listing of the FERs is in the WorldFAIR FAIR Convergence Matrix¹⁴¹.

	IUPAC Gold Book	IUPAC Standards	Nanomaterials (safety)	NanoPharos database	GeoROC	AGN-AusGeoch em	EarthChem Library	GFZ data services -Geosciences	Social Surveys ESS	Social Surveys AussiESS	INSPIRE Covid19	Urban Health	SALURBAL	Global Biodiversity (GBIF)	Pollinator interactions	Ocean Data (ODIS)	Disaster Risk Reduction	Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI)
F1.1-MD	1	1	8	4	1	4	1	1	1	1	2	1	3	3	1	3	3	3
F1.1-D	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	3	3	1	2
F2	2	0	8	2	1	3	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	7	1	1	5	6
F3	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
F4-MD	1	1	4	1	1	0	4	2	2	1	1	1	1	3	2	2	2	2
F4-D	1	1	4	1	0	0	2	1	2	1	0	1	0	3	2	1	1	1
A1.1-MD	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2
A1.1-D	2	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	0	1	1	2	3	2	1	1
A1.2-MD	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
A1.2-D	0	0	2	1	0	0	1	1	3	1	0	1	0	0	3	0	1	2
A2	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
I1-MD	1	6	6	7	2	0	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	0	4	7	1	3
I1-D	1	5	3	0	1	0	1	1	1	5	1	1	0	2	4	1	1	1
I2-MD	0	1	3	3	0	2	1	4	1	2	0	3	0	2	2	4	1	11
I2-D	0	1	2	0	0	5	1	4	8	0	0	1	0	1	2	3	1	1
I3-MD	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	3	2	1	1	2
I3-D	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	6	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
R1.1-MD	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	3	1	1	2
R1.1-D	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	1	2	9
R1.2-MD	1	1	2	1	0	0	0	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	2	0	2
R1.2-D	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	3	1	1	1	0	0	1	2	0	2

¹⁴¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11397305>

Figure 2. Graph visualisation showing the connections between WP09 Biodiversity and WP10 Agricultural Biodiversity.

The FERs used in both case studies' FIPs are shown in the middle. It is perhaps not surprising that this combination of WPs displays one of the richest sets of connections.

Figure 3. Graph visualisation showing the connections between WP11 Ocean Sciences and WP12 Disaster Risk Reduction.

This graph shows a number of points of connection between Ocean Sciences and Disaster Risk Reduction. These could be considerably increased, not least by the adoption of further cross-domain standards in the many sub-fields and data sources of DRR. It should be noted that this graph uses the first draft FIP from WP11 Ocean Sciences, which is deprecated given the preference of ODIS to express their FIP using a different format.

Figure 4. Graph visualisation showing the connections between WP03 Chemistry, WP04 Nanomaterials, and WP05 Geochemistry.

This graph shows the many areas of connection between the three WorldFAIR work packages dealing with chemistry and materials related research. Reproducing the image for this report results in the information about **which** FERs are shared is lost, but the graph remains useful to show the numbers of connections. The full image can be consulted at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11397387>.

With these examples, one can grasp immediately how, at scale, such analysis and visualisation could be incredibly valuable. For that promise to be realised the (real and perceived) frictions to creating FIPs and publishing them need to be reduced. Another challenge, remarked on above, is differences caused by whether a FIP is characterising the use of FERs for a dataset, a collection, a repository or the practices of a community. This means that, among the WorldFAIR case studies, it is not always possible to compare like with like. Yet for all these challenges, it is clear that the FIPs approach has genuine benefits and huge potential if it can be conducted at scale.

What is impossible to show through such visualisations, is how useful the WorldFAIR case studies found the FIPs exercises (particularly the initial discussions around a spreadsheet) and the conversations and comparisons it subsequently sparked. There were in these conversations throughout the project a number of lightbulb moments of the nature: ‘Oh yes, we use that FER too!’ or ‘Oh, maybe we should look into that!’

7.1 Examples of influence of FIPs across domains / case studies

Some of the most notable examples of influence of FIPs across the domains and case studies have been mentioned above. These are important examples of impact that came out of the collective FIPs discussions or the CDIF workshops, or other interactions among the work packages. Specifically these are:

1. the programmed adoption of DDI standards in WP08 (Urban Health, SALURBAL);
2. the alignment in approaches observed in the use of JSON-LD/schema.org between WP11 (Ocean Science, ODIS) and WP07 (Population Health, INSPIRE);
3. the adoption of IGSNs from Work Package 5 (GeoSciences) by WP04 Nanomaterials;
4. the adoption of PROV-O and the events-centred approach from WP09 (Biodiversity) by WP04 (Nanomaterials).

These are four very positive outcomes from the FIPs exercise and from the project as a whole.

8. Conclusions

The observations of the D1.3 Policy Brief¹⁴² remain broadly applicable across the WorldFAIR project as a whole: “As recommended in the Turning FAIR into Reality report, ‘Research communities need to be supported to develop interoperability frameworks that define their practices for data sharing, data formats, metadata standards, tools and infrastructure.’ The FIPs exercises undertaken by the WorldFAIR project are a good approach and will be more effective if they are international in scope.”

¹⁴² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7853170>

¹⁴³ Further, “the FIPs exercise was valuable in helping us better understand the complex data practices in each of the Case Study communities. The process and methodology were also useful in helping construct a picture encompassing both the current state of practice in relation to FAIR and the possible aspirations for greater FAIR implementation in the field of research of each Case Study.”

¹⁴⁴ **For these reasons, the WorldFAIR project strongly supports the use of FIPs by the global data stewardship community and recommends that investment is made to socialise the approach, and to improve and sustain the necessary infrastructures.**

The experience of the WorldFAIR project was that the FIPs exercises were enlightening and useful, both for the Case Studies and the cross-project synthesis work. The project identified a number of highly beneficial uses for FIPs: as didactic tools; as a useful mechanism for normative declarations of good practice; as a basis for targeted and detailed, domain-specific FAIR assessment; and as a mechanism for identifying commonalities across disciplines and cross-domain solutions. There was some discussion about the optimal level at which a FIP should be conducted. Notably, it was found that there is an evident utility for FIPs to be developed at the dataset- and the repository- or data service-level. There were recommendations, notably as discussed above from WP05 (Geochemistry), for research disciplines to self-organise globally and encourage FIPs to be developed and published at each of these levels. Similarly, it was argued that ‘authoritative organisations’ which represent particular disciplines globally (e.g. as represented in the WorldFAIR project by international scientific unions like IUPAC, community initiatives like OneGeochemistry, standards bodies like DDI, or global research infrastructures like ODIS and GBIF) have a role and responsibility to make sure that the FERs for which they are responsible are published in such a way that they can be referenced in FIPs. **Consequently, the WorldFAIR project is strongly supportive of the FIPs approach. A global graph of FERs and FIPs could be a resource of considerable power and benefit.**

The WorldFAIR project identified a number of current barriers to achieving this. These include the effort required to create FERs and FIPs (including usability issues with the FIP Wizard) and ease of visualisation (which would provide more immediate value and a sense of reward for the process). It has been argued that these barriers could be (at least partly) overcome by the wholesale integration of FER information from FAIRsharing and a change in the technical underpinnings.

To accelerate progress towards achieving this vision of a global graph of FERs and FIPs, it would be hugely beneficial to find a mechanism for the wholesale integration of FAIRsharing entries as FERs that can be identified in FIPs. Is such a solution organisationally and technically possible? **The WorldFAIR project recommends that options to enable the wholesale use of FAIRsharing information as FERs in FIPs be explored by the parties involved and by the community as a whole.**

¹⁴³ Hodson, S., and Gregory, A. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D1.3) First policy brief (Version 1), p.11. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7853170>

¹⁴⁴ Hodson, S., and Gregory, A. (2023), p.6. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7853170>

It was also argued, as described above by WorldFAIR WP11 (Ocean Sciences), that a shift from the use of nanopublications to JSON-LD/schema.org would provide technological underpinnings that better allow the creation of tools to analyse and visualise FIPs, facilitating the engagement of a wider developer base. Based on a widely-used web format, it would also be easier to harvest declared FIPs and FERs for this purpose. In response, the GO FAIR Foundation team behind the FIPs initiative contend that this would result in semantic loss (particularly in relation to the provenance of the statement and the way in which the nanopublication wraps the set of declarations in FERs and FIPs). Is it possible to find a way of harmonising the nanopublication approach favoured by GO FAIR with the JSON-LD/schema.org approach suggested above? **The WorldFAIR project recommends that effort is dedicated to aligning and harmonising these approaches in order to enable the FAIR community and the multitude of disciplines to achieve the objectives of the FIPs approach and vision.**

In responding to Recommendation 4 of the ‘Turning FAIR into Reality’ report¹⁴⁵, WorldFAIR has been motivated by a conviction that any assessment of FAIR practices needs to be informed by the requirements of research domains and cross-domain research areas. In approaches to FAIR assessment, the question set underlying the tool has been concerned with *whether* the repository or dataset uses (for example) a FAIR compliant identifier or vocabulary. In contrast, the FIPs question set asks the user to specify *which* vocabulary (or other FER) is being used. This is a far more useful exercise. In time, FIPs can provide a model against which FAIR assessment can be based, reflecting both the current practice, and the aspirations of a given community or research domain. A number of the case studies argued that the utility of FIPs and FERs could be increased even more by adding further information about *how* the FER is implemented, adding an important dimension for data and metadata validation. **In time, if CDIF plays the role envisaged, it will be useful for FIPs to make specific reference to how the CDIF recommendations and profiles are implemented.**

9. Recommendations

What follows is a summary of the most important recommendations that have emerged from the WorldFAIR experience of using FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and the synthesis and discussion above. (For each recommendation, the recommendation type and its intended audience are indicated in brackets.)

1. **Provide policy support and investment for FIPs:** Funders and policy makers, through investment and appropriate policy direction, should support the global data stewardship community to socialise the FIPs approach, and to improve and sustain the necessary infrastructures. (Policy; policy makers and funders)

¹⁴⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/7769a148-f1f6-11e8-9982-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/>

2. **Publish FERs:** Representative and authoritative organisations that are responsible for particular FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) should describe and publish these FERs in a way that they can be easily referenced in FIPs. They should be supported and enabled in doing so by other stakeholders, i.e. funders, policy makers and the data stewardship community at large. (Organisational; authoritative/representative organisations, standards organisations, data repositories).
3. **Make it easier to publish FERs and FIPs:** Supported by the global data stewardship community, the GO FAIR Foundation (GFF) should explore solutions to lower the barriers to information entry to the FIPs ecosystem, including by ensuring a wider range of import and export profiles. The GFF should be enabled to do so by well-targeted funding to enable the development and sustainability of the necessary infrastructures. (Organisational; GFF, data stewardship community, funders, policy makers).
 - a. Specifically, JSON-LD import and export should be developed and enabled in the FIPs Wizard and FAIR Connect.¹⁴⁶
 - b. Specifically, the GFF (and any other stakeholders using systems that will interoperate) should enable a distinction to be made between ‘no answer given’ (e.g. due to lack of maturity of the community) and ‘not applicable’ (e.g. because the community has determined that no declaration is necessary, no resource is needed for this sub-principle).
4. **Make it easier to visualise FIPs:** Collectively, the global data stewardship community and the GFF should explore numerous avenues to improve the way in which FIPs and FERs can be visualised and analysed. This endeavour should be enabled by well-targeted funding and direction from policy makers. (Organisational; GFF, data stewardship community, funders, policy makers).
5. **Enable the wholesale use of FAIRsharing entries as FERs in FIPs:** GFF and FAIRsharing, supported by the global data stewardship community and other stakeholders, should explore mechanisms to enable the wholesale use of FAIRsharing information as FERs in FIPs. Such a process should be supported by well-targeted funding and direction from policy makers. (Technical; GFF, FAIRsharing, data stewardship community, funders, policy makers).
6. **Review optimal encoding of FIPs and explore alignment:** GFF, ODIS, the CDIF WG and AG, and global data stewardship community, should constructively review the pros and cons of the technical underpinnings to the current FIPs approach and explore whether an alignment of the nanopublications approach and the suggested JSON-LD/schema.org approach could be achieved. Such a process should be supported by well-targeted funding and direction

¹⁴⁶ Since the draft version of this report was shared with colleagues at the GFF, a JSON-LD export has been enabled for the FIP Wizard.

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from policy makers. (Technical; GFF, FAIRsharing, data stewardship community, funders, policy makers).

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